

New species of Pruvotininae (Solenogastres, Cavibelonia) from bathyal bottoms off the NW Iberian Peninsula, with a taxonomical discussion about the family Pruvotinidae

Nuevas especies de Pruvotininae (Solenogastres, Cavibelonia) de los fondos batiales del NO de la Península Ibérica, con una discusión taxonómica sobre Pruvotinidae

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Recibido el 26-II-2022. Aceptado el 1-VI-2022

ABSTRACT

The family Pruvotinidae (Solenogastres, Cavibelonia) comprises 34 species grouped in 15 genera, five subfamilies and one uncertain subfamily. Three genera with 15 species make up the subfamily Pruvotininae characterized by hook-shaped, hollow acicular sclerites, dorso-pharyngeal gland and ventrolateral foregut glands type A or type *Pararrhopalia*. Seven species of this subfamily new to science are described in this paper: *Pararrhopalia oscari* Pedrouzo & Urgorri n. sp., *Pruvotina glandulosa* n. sp., *Pruvotina bathyalis* n. sp., *Pruvotina zamorroae* n. sp., *Pruvotina harpagone* n. sp., *Labidoherpia vitucoi* Pedrouzo & García-Álvarez n. sp. and *Labidoherpia lucus* n. sp. from hard substrata of bathyal bottoms of NW Iberian Peninsula at a depth of 438 - 2516 m. In addition, the midgut with regular constrictions of *Pararrhopalia pruvoti* Simroth, 1893 and *Pararrhopalia oscari* n. sp. and the harpoon-shaped sclerites of *Pruvotina harpagone* n. sp. have led to modify the diagnosis of the genera *Pararrhopalia*, *Pruvotina* and *Labidoherpia*. *Pararrhopalia pruvoti* Simroth, 1893 is redescribed. In the taxonomical discussion about the family Pruvotinidae, the classification of the genus *Forcepimonia* Salvini-Plawen, 1969 in the subfamily Halomeniinae Salvini-Plawen, 1978 and of the genus *Scheltemaia* Salvini-Plawen, 2003 in the new subfamily Scheltemaiinae is proposed. The classification of the family Pruvotinidae is summarized.

RESUMEN

La familia Pruvotinidae (Solenogastres, Cavibelonia) comprende 34 especies agrupadas en 15 géneros, cinco subfamilias y una subfamilia incierta. Tres géneros con 15 especies componen la subfamilia Pruvotininae caracterizada por escleritos aciculares huecos en forma de gancho, glándula dorsofaringea y glándulas ventrolaterales de la faringe tipo A o tipo *Pararrhopalia*. En este artículo se describen para esta subfamilia siete especies nuevas para la ciencia: *Pararrhopalia oscari* Pedrouzo & Urgorri n. sp., *Pruvotina glandulosa* n. sp., *Pruvotina bathyalis* n. sp., *Pruvotina zamorroae* n. sp., *Pruvotina harpagone* n. sp., *Labidoherpia vitucoi* Pedrouzo & García-Álvarez n. sp. y *Labidoherpia lucus* n. sp. de sustratos duros en fondos batiales del NO de la Península Ibérica a una profundidad de 438 - 2516 m. Además, las constricciones regulares en el intestino de *Pararrhopalia pruvoti*

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Simroth, 1893 y *Pararrhopalia oscari* n. sp. y los escleritos en forma de arpón de *Pruvotina harpagone* n. sp. ha llevado a modificar las diagnosis de los géneros *Pararrhopalia*, *Pruvotina* y *Labidoherpia*. Se redescubre *Pararrhopalia pruvoti* Simroth, 1893. En la discusión taxonómica sobre la familia Pruvotinidae, se propone clasificar al género *Forcepimonia* Salvini-Plawen, 1969 en la subfamilia Halomeniinae Salvini-Plawen, 1978 y al género *Scheltemaia* Salvini-Plawen, 2003 en la nueva subfamilia Scheltemaiinae. Se resume la clasificación de la familia Pruvotinidae.

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:CA638E7E-B881-47EA-AA4B-4867DFE6F610

KEY WORDS: New species, Pruvotininae, Pruvotinidae, Solenogastres, bathyal, NW Iberian Peninsula.
PALABRAS CLAVE: Nuevas especies, Pruvotininae, Pruvotinidae, Solenogastres, batial, NO Península Ibérica.

INTRODUCTION

Solenogastres are vermiform marine molluscs with an aculiferan mantle with calcarean sclerites, a longitudinal ventral pedal groove and an either terminal or subterminal pallial cavity without ctenidia. They are benthic epifaunal animals in different types of substrata or epizoic on colonial Cnidaria on which they feed (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1972; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ, SALVINI-PLAWEN AND URGORRI, 2014).

Class Solenogastres (*sensu* Salvini-Plawen, 1978) comprises around 300 species grouped in 23 families and four orders. Family Pruvotinidae Heath, 1911 is one of the 12 families of the order Cavibelonia comprising more than 50% of the species of the solenogaster species. Pruvotinidae is a complex family made up of 34 species grouped in 15 genera, five subfamilies and one subfamily incerta characterized by the combination of the type of mantle sclerites, the presence or absence of a dorso-pharyngeal gland and the type of ventrolateral foregut glands (GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ AND SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2007). The subfamily Pruvotininae Heath, 1911 (=Pararrhopaliinae Salvini-Plawen, 1978) is characterized by bearing hook-shaped hollow acicular sclerites, dorso-pharyngeal gland and ventrolateral foregut glands type A (according to SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ AND SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2007) or *Pararrhopalia* (according to HANDL AND TODT,

2005). It includes three genera with 15 species.

The genus *Pararrhopalia* Simroth, 1893 comprises two species: *Pararrhopalia fasciata* Salvini-Plawen, 1978 described from the Antarctic Ocean and *Pararrhopalia pruvoti* Simroth, 1893 described from the Western Mediterranean and Atlantic Ocean (NW Iberian Peninsula) (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ AND SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2007; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ, SALVINI-PLAWEN AND URGORRI, 2014).

Twelve species are included in the genus *Pruvotina* Cockerell, 1903. Eight of the species of this genus have been described from the Antarctic Ocean: *Pruvotina cryophila* (Pelseneer, 1901), *Pruvotina gauszi* Salvini-Plawen, 1978, *Pruvotina longispinosa* Salvini-Plawen, 1978, *Pruvotina pallioglandulata* Salvini-Plawen, 1978, *Pruvotina praegnans* Salvini-Plawen, 1978, *Pruvotina providens* Thiele, 1913, *Pruvotina uniperata* Salvini-Plawen, 1978 and *Pruvotina manifesta* Zamarro, García-Álvarez and Ugorri, 2013; two from Tierra de Fuego: *Pruvotina megathecata* Salvini-Plawen, 1978 and *Pruvotina peniculata* Salvini-Plawen, 1978. However, only two species are European, *Pruvotina impexa* (Pruvot, 1890) described from Bayunls-sur Mer (Mediterranean Sea) and *Pruvotina artabra* Zamarro, García-Álvarez and Ugorri, 2013 from the NW Iberian Peninsula (Atlantic Ocean) (PRUVOT,

1890; PELSENEER, 1901; THIELE, 1913; SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ AND SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2007; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ *ET AL.*, 2014; ZAMARRO, GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ AND URGORRI, 2013).

Labidoherpia Salvini-Plawen, 1978, is a monospecific genus whose only species, *Labidoherpia spinosa* (Thiele, 1913), was described from the Antarctic Ocean (Thiele, 1913; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ AND SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2007).

In this paper, seven species of the subfamily Pruvotininae are described as new to science: *Pararrhopalia oscar* Pedrouzo & Urgorri n. sp., *Pruvotina glandulosa* n. sp., *Pruvotina bathyalis* n. sp., *Pruvotina zamarroae* n. sp., *Pruvotina harpagone* n. sp., *Labidoherpia vituconi* Pedrouzo & García-Álvarez n. sp. and *Labidoherpia lucus* n. sp. from hard substrata of bathyal bottoms of NW Iberian Peninsula. *Pararrhopalia pruvoti* is redescribed, providing new data and anatomical reconstructions (Fig. 5D). In addition, the classification of the genus *Scheltemaia* Salvini-Plawen, 2003 in the new subfamily Scheltemaiinae and of the genus *Forcepimania* Salvini-Plawen, 1969 in the subfamily Halomeniinae Salvini-Plawen, 1978 is proposed. Finally, the classification of the family Pruvotinidae is summarized.

RESULTS

(Systematics following GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ & SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2007)

Order CAVIBELONIA Salvini-Plawen, 1978

Family PRUVOTINIDAE Heath, 1911

With hollow acicular sclerites. With or without hook-shaped hollow sclerites. Radula distichous or missing. With or without dorso-pharyngeal gland. ventrolateral foregut glands of ducts with either subepithelially/extraepithe-

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This work includes the study of 42 specimens of Solenogastres collected on bathyal bottoms of NW Iberian Peninsula at a depth of 438 to 2516 m during the expeditions DIVA-Artabria I 2003, DIVA-Artabria II 2008 and A Selva 2008 (Table I) carried out by the Estación de Biología Mariña de A Graña (University of Santiago de Compostela, Spain). Specimens were fixed and preserved in neutralized ethanol (70%). Animals were photographed and measured, and the external anatomy was described. Sclerites were studied directly on the animal and by separating small pieces of the mantle from the dorsal and lateral areas of the body. These pieces were treated with 5% sodium hypochlorite for 12 h in order to isolate the sclerites; they were later rinsed with water, dried in a heater at 40°C and mounted using Araldite for examination by light microscopy. For their anatomical study, specimens were decalcified with EDTA solution for 12 h, and the anterior and posterior region of the specimens were embedded in paraffin, cut in serial transverse 5 µm sections and stained with Mallory's trichromic stain. Histological examination and reconstruction were done under an Olympus microscope.

lially arranged gland cells (type A), or circumpharyngeal subepithelial/extraepithelial follicular glands, or with epithelial/ intraepithelial gland cells (type C). With or without respiratory folds.

Subfamily PRUVOTININAE Heath, 1911

With hook-shaped hollow sclerites. Ventrolateral foregut glands of ducts with subepithelially/ extrae-

pithelially arranged gland cells (type A). With a dorso-pharyngeal gland.

Genus *Pararrhopalia* Simroth, 1893 (amended)

Type species: *Pararrhopalia pruvoti* Simroth, 1893.

With tangential sclerites in two or more layers. With epidermal papillae. Without harpoon-shaped sclerites. Mouth separated from the atrium. Distichous radula.

Midgut with regular constrictions. Secondary genital opening unpaired. With copulatory stylets. With dorsoterminal sense organ. Without respiratory folds.

Pararrhopalia pruvoti Simroth, 1893 (Figs. 1, 3, 5)

Material examined: SPAIN • 1 specimen (Table I, specimen 1) cut in 5 μ m serial cross sections; 43° 23.22' N, 09° 32.30' W to 43° 42.28' N, 09° 30.83' W; 733 - 862 m; DIVA-Artabria II 2008 station 31-EBS; bottom of polymetallic nodules with stones • 1 specimen (Table I, specimen 2) cut in 5 μ m serial cross sections; 44° 09.896' N, 08° 39.581' W to 44° 10.129' N, 08° 39.494' W; 438-459 m; A Selva 2008 station 11-DRN; bottom of polymetallic nodules with slightly muddy sand.

Distribution: Banyuls-sur Mer (France) at a depth of 80 m on muddy bottoms among Hydrozoa and Bryozoa (PRUVOT, 1891). NW Iberian Peninsula at a depth of 150 - 600 m (TODT, 2006; SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2008).

Description: *Habitus:* Body 1.42 - 4.69 mm long and 0.31 - 0.52 mm wide (Fig. 1A). With sclerites protruding from the body, especially in the posterior region. Longitudinal pedal groove well-marked externally. Subterminal pallial cavity.

Mantle: Thin cuticle, 35-40 μ m thick, with epidermal papillae. Blade-shaped scales on the pedal groove (35-45 μ m long; 8 μ m maximum wide) (Fig. 3C) and five types of hollow acicular sclerites: hook-shaped (90-150 μ m long; 7.5 μ m wide) with a tooth on the curvature (Fig. 3A); small, rectilinear and narrow (50-150 μ m long; 2-3 μ m wide); sigmoid (75-180 μ m long; 8-3 μ m wide) with curved proximal end; arched in the middle region (50-280 μ m long; 2-3 μ m wide) (Fig. 3B); and serrated (100 μ m long; 2.5 μ m wide), arranged in the anterior region.

Pedal groove and pallial cavity: Pedal pit (35 μ m long, 100 μ m high, 95 μ m wide) densely ciliated. Pedal groove with a medial fold ending at the beginning of the pallial cavity. Pallial cavity opening in ventral position (Fig. 5D), walls folded, however, not forming real respiratory folds.

Nervous system: Unpaired cerebral ganglion (65 μ m long, 65 μ m high, 120

μ m wide) of oval cross section with three pairs of frontal nerves and a distal widening on the posterior region of the atrium. With a pair of buccal ganglia (20 μ m wide) in the radular region of the pharynx (Fig. 5D). Wide suprarectal commissure (15 μ m long), located dorsally to the rectum in the final section of the pericardi ducts (Fig. 5D).

Sense organs: Simple, double and some triple papillae in to the lateral and dorsal walls of the atrial cavity (Fig. 5A). A pre-atrial sense organ (15 μ m long; 25 μ m wide) can be observed in the dorso-anterior region of the atrium (Fig. 5A, d). Without dorsoterminal sense organ.

Digestive system: The mouth opens to the outside separated from the atrium (Fig. 5D) and continues in a narrow pharynx (110 μ m long, 55 μ m high and 60 μ m wide) surrounded by a strong layer of circular musculature. A dorso-pharyngeal gland (35 μ m long, 40 μ m wide) opens into the pre-radular region of the pharynx (Fig. 5D). The radular apparatus comprises a distichous radula and a radular sac (Fig. 5B, D). The radular teeth (25 μ m long) bear a very sharp distal hook. At the base of the tooth, four medial elongated denticles (Fig. 5B) are observed (3 μ m high and 0.5 - 1 μ m wide at the base). Ventrolateral foregut glands (Fig. 5B-D) tubular, short and narrow (35 μ m long, 30 μ m high, 20 μ m wide) of type A (following SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ

Table I. Examined specimens of Pruvotininae Heath, 1911.

Tabla I. Especímenes examinados de Pruvotininae Heath, 1911.

Expedition	Station	Depth (m)	Coord.	N° specimens	Substratum	Species
DIVA-artabria I 2003	600 - DRN	600	43° 48.421' N; 08° 51.453' W - 43° 49.160' N; 08° 51.091' W	1	stones	<i>Pruvotina zamarroae</i> n. sp.
DIVA artabria I 2003	600 - AT	616	43° 48,514' N; 08° 51.439' W - 43° 49,163' N; 08° 51.157' W	1	stones	<i>Labidoherpia lucus</i> n. sp.
DIVA-artabria II 2008	25 - EBS	709 - 728	42° 55.76' N; 09° 44.04' W - 42° 55.79' N; 09° 44.57' W	3	rocky	<i>Pruvotina harpagone</i> n. sp.
DIVA-artabria II 2008	31 - EBS	733 - 862	43° 2.22' N; 09° 32.30' W - 43° 42.28' N; 09° 30.83' W	1	polymetallic nodules with stones	<i>Pararrhopalia pruvoti</i>
DIVA-artabria II 2008	26 - DRN - p	1177 - 1861	42° 51.20' N; 09° 43.85' W - 42° 52.97' N; 09° 44.25' W	2	coral	<i>Pruvotina zamarroae</i> n. sp.
A SELVA 2008	11 - DRN	438 - 459	44° 09.896' N; 08° 39.581' W - 44° 10.129' N; 08° 39.494' W	1 3 2	polymetallic nodules with slightly muddy sand	<i>Pararrhopalia pruvoti</i> <i>Pararrhopalia oscar</i> n. sp. <i>Labidoherpia vitucoi</i> n. sp.
A SELVA 2008	7 - C	566 - 581	44° 08.65' N; 08° 55.305' W - 44° 08.771' N; 08° 55.104' W	1	dead corals	<i>Pruvotina bathyalis</i> n. sp.
A SELVA 2008	30 - 1 - EBS	575 - 584	43° 48.252' N; 08° 51.427' W - 43° 49.707' N; 08° 51.164' W	6	polymetallic nodes with muddy sand	<i>Pruvotina bathyalis</i> n. sp.
A SELVA 2008	15 - 2 - DRN	620 - 933	43° 56.478' N; 08° 54.199' W - 43° 55.934' N; 08° 54.849' W	1	mud with coral	<i>Pruvotina zamarroae</i> n. sp.
A SELVA 2008	7 - DRN	908 - 1106	44° 11.652' N; 08° 58.152' W - 44° 11.539' N; 08° 57.574' W	19	sand with coral	<i>Pruvotina glandulosa</i> n. sp.
A SELVA 2008	12 - AT	2121 - 2516	44° 14.929' N; 08° 30.255' W - 44° 15.367' N; 08° 30.438' W	1	large stones, polymetallic nodules and muddy sand with some coral	<i>Pruvotina bathyalis</i> n. sp.

AND SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2007) or *Pararrhopalia* (following HANDL AND TODT, 2005). They open laterally into the radular region and run upwards without reaching the midgut. The oesophagus (75 μm long, 60 μm high and 40 μm wide) opens in the middle region of the midgut (Fig. 5C, D) through a muscular sphincter (30 μm wide). The midgut is prolonged in a short and paired anterodorsal caecum (25 μm long, 25 μm high, 105 μm wide) at its anterior end (Fig. 5C, D). In addition, it has constrictions and serial side pouches along its whole length. The rectum opens into the dorsoanterior wall of the pallial cavity (Fig. 5D).

Gonopericardial system: Gonads with spermatozoa in specimen 2 (Fig. 5E). Gonads are connected by the gonopericardioducts with a voluminous peri-

cardium (265 μm long, 50 μm high, 60 μm wide) (Fig. 5D). The heart (85 μm long, 30 μm high, 45 μm wide) is located within the pericardium as an invagination of the dorsal wall (Fig. 5D). A pair of small seminal vesicles (25 - 80 μm long, 15 μm high, 10 μm wide) are located in the middle region of the pericardioducts (Fig. 5D). A pair of lateral pouches (55 μm long, 85 μm wide) are located on the ventroposterior wall of the spawning duct (Fig. 5D, F). The genital orifice opens on the ventroanterior wall of the pallial cavity (Fig. 5D). With two bundles (30 μm wide) of 16 copulatory stylets each (Fig. 5D-G). They come out from the region of the gonopericardioducts and open to the exterior anteriorly to the opening of the pallial cavity, surrounded by a strong muscular mass.

Pararrhopalia oscar Pedrouzo and Urgorri n. sp. (Figs. 1, 3, 6)

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Type material. *Holotype:* SPAIN • 1 specimen cut in 5 μm serial cross-sections; 44° 09.896' N, 08° 39.581' W to 44° 10.129' N, 08° 39.494' W; 438-459 m; A Selva 2008 station 11-DRN; bottom of poly-metallic nodules with slightly muddy sand; Museo de Historia Natural of the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain) MHNUSC n° 10075. *Paratypes:* SPAIN • 1 specimen (paratype 1) cut in 5 μm serial cross-sections; same locality data as for holotype; Museo de Historia Natural of the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain) MHNUSC n° 10076 • 1 juvenile specimen (paratype 2) cut in 5 μm serial cross-sections; same data as for the holotype; collection of the Zoology and P.A. Department of the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain).

Etymology: The species is dedicated to Dr. Óscar García-Álvarez, specialist in the study of Mollusca Solenogastres and Caudofoveata.

Diagnosis: Moderately thick cuticle with epidermal papillae. With six types of sclerites: one hook-shaped acicular sclerite, four hollows acicular sclerite and one scale - type on the pedal groove. With three folds on the pedal groove. With a pre-atrial sense organ. Atrial papillae simple, double, and triple. With dorsal gland. Distichous radula. Radular teeth with acute distal hook and six medial denticles. Ventrolateral foregut glands tubular, long and narrow (type A). Oesophagus with sphincter. With a short anterodorsal caecum of the midgut. Pericardium with terminal pouches. With very voluminous seminal

receptacles. Spawning duct with a pair of lateral pouches. Unpaired genital orifice opening in the anterior region of the pallial cavity. Pallial cavity divided in two regions. With a pair of bundles of 12 - 15 copulatory stylets. With dorsoterminal sense organ.

Description: *Habitus:* Animals 3.72 - 6.6 mm long by 0.52 - 0.73 mm wide in the anterior region and 0.36 - 0.65 mm in the posterior region (Fig. 1B). No keels or crests. Sclerites projecting from the body, especially in the posterior region. Pallial cavity in ventral position.

Mantle: Cuticle (55 - 75 μm thick) with epidermal papillae. Blade-shaped

Figures 1, 2. Habitus. 1A: *Pararrhopalia pruvoti* Simroth, 1893; 1B: *Pararrhopalia oscari* sp.nov.; 1C: *Labidoherpia vitucoi* n. sp.; 1D: *Labidoherpia lucus* n. sp.; 2A: *Pruvotina glandulosa* n. sp.; 2B: *Pruvotina bathyalis* sp.nov.; 2C: *Pruvotina zamarroae* n. sp.; 2D: *Pruvotina harpagone* n. sp.
 Figuras 1, 2. Habitus. 1A: *Pararrhopalia pruvoti* Simroth, 1893; 1B: *Pararrhopalia oscari* sp.nov.; 1C: *Labidoherpia vitucoi* n. sp.; 1D: *Labidoherpia lucus* n. sp.; 2A: *Pruvotina glandulosa* n. sp.; 2B: *Pruvotina bathyalis* sp.nov.; 2C: *Pruvotina zamarroae* n. sp.; 2D: *Pruvotina harpagone* n. sp.

scales on the pedal groove (50 - 100 μm long and 9 - 15 μm wide) and five types of hollow acicular sclerites obliquely inserted and radially intercrossed, arranged in three layers: hook-shaped (135 - 170 μm long, 10 μm wide) with a tooth on the curvature; rectilinear (60 - 215 μm long, 10 - 12 μm wide) (Fig. 3D); sigmoid (135 - 245 μm long, 10 - 15 μm wide) (Fig. 3E); arched in the middle region (60 - 225 μm long, 10 - 15 μm wide); serrated arranged in the posterior region (Fig. 3F).

Pedal groove and pallial cavity: Pedal pit densely ciliated (35 μm long, 100 μm high, 95 μm wide). Pedal groove with three folds ending at the beginning of the pallial cavity: a larger central one (50 μm high, 35 μm wide at the base) and two smaller lateral ones (20 μm high, 15 μm wide at the base). Anterior pedal glands highly developed. Pallial cavity opening in ventral position, covered by a folded wall without forming real respiratory folds (Fig. 6G). Pallial cavity divided in two regions (anterior and posterior) separated by a vertical septum with musculature (Fig. 6D).

Nervous system: Unpaired and oval cerebral ganglion (45 μm long, 75 μm high and 70 μm wide). With a pair of ventral ganglia (50 μm long, 50 μm wide) and a pair of buccal ganglia of circular section (30 μm wide). Suprarectal commissure (20 μm long) located dorsally to the terminal pouches of the pericardium (Fig. 6D, G).

Sense organs Simple, double and some triple papillae on the lateral and dorsal walls of the atrial cavity (Fig. 6A). A pre-atrial sense organ (25 μm long, 25 μm high and 100 μm wide) is located in the dorsoanterior region of the atrium (Fig. 6A-D). With a well-developed dor-

soterminal sense organ (75 μm long, 85 μm high and 100 μm wide) (Fig. 6D).

Digestive system: Atrium and mouth separated by a small muscular groove without cuticle. Narrow pharynx (335 μm long, 50 - 185 μm high and 100 - 125 μm wide) and with an anterior caecum reaching the atrium (Fig. 6D). A dorso-pharyngeal gland (Fig. 6D) opens into the pre-radular region of the pharynx (75 μm long, 95 μm high and 115 μm wide). Radular apparatus comprising a distichous radula and a radular sac (Fig. 6B-D). Large radular teeth, approximately 40 μm long, with a distal hook wide and curved (10 μm) and a narrow base (7.5 μm). They bear six small and pointed denticles, all in the same size (Fig. 6B), approximately 5 μm high and 3 μm wide at the base. Ventrolateral foregut glands (Fig. 6C, D) tubular and narrow (345 μm long, 30 μm wide) type A (following SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ AND SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2007) or type *Pararrhopalia* (following HANDL AND TODT, 2005). They open laterally at the beginning of the radular sac and run upwards until reaching the midgut. Oesophagus long and narrow (130 μm long, 75 μm high, 80 μm wide), final section surrounded by layers of longitudinal musculature (Fig. 6C). It enters the midgut to open in the middle region through a sphincter (Fig. 6D). The midgut extends anteriorly in a short unpaired anterodorsal caecum (Fig. 6D) (70 μm long, 65 μm high, 150 μm wide), the midgut shows serial lateral constrictions and lateral pouches along its entire length. Rectum open dorsally into the pallial cavity (Fig. 6D).

Gonopericardial system: The tubular gonads contain oocytes in the posterior region. The pericardium (265 μm long,

(Right page) Figure 3. Optical microscope microphotographs of the types of sclerites. A-C: *Pararrhopalia pruvoti* Simroth, 1893 (A: hook-shaped with a tooth on the curvature; B: arched in the middle region; C: blade - shaped scales on the pedal groove); D-F: *Pararrhopalia oscari* n. sp. (D: rectilinear; E: sigmoid; F: serrated); G-I: *Labidoherpia vituoi* n. sp. (G: hook-shaped with a tooth on the curvature; H: sigmoid; I: blade - shaped scales on the pedal groove); J-L: *Labidoherpia lucus* n. sp. (J: hook-shaped with a tooth on the curvature; K: rectilinear long and narrow; L: arched in the middle region).

Figura 3. Microfotografías al microscopio óptico de los tipos de escleritos. A-C: *Pararrhopalia pruvoti* Simroth, 1893 (A: forma de gancho con un diente en la curvatura; B: arqueado en la región media; C: escama en forma de cuchillo del surco pedio); D-F: *Pararrhopalia oscari* sp. nov. (D: rectilíneo; E: sigmoideo; F: aserrado); G-I: *Labidoherpia vitucoi* n. sp. (G: forma de gancho con un diente en la curvatura; H: sigmoideo; I: escama en forma de cuchillo del surco pedio); J-L: *Labidoherpia lucus* n. sp. (J: forma de gancho con un diente en la curvatura; K: rectilíneo, largo y estrecho; L: arqueado en la región media).

50 μm high, 60 μm wide) includes the heart in its dorsal wall. The terminal region of the pericardium extends in three pouches approximately 80 μm high, 75 μm high and 65 μm wide (Fig. 6D-G). With a pair of voluminous seminal receptacles (265 μm long, 40 μm high, 50 μm wide) forming a large pouch in their anterior region where the pericardioducts open, whereas the spawning ducts open into their ventral wall (Fig. 6D-F). The seminal receptacles narrow posteriorly until reaching the terminal pouches of the pericardium. With two bundles (50 μm wide) of 12 - 15 copulatory stylets each (Fig. 6D-F). The copulatory stylets come out at the level of the gonopericardioducts and end before the opening of the pallial cavity. Their entire length is surrounded by musculature, which in its posterior region forms a muscular pouch opening outwards.

Taxonomical discussion: The studied specimens of *Pararrhopalia pruvoti* Simroth, 1893, come from Atlantic Ocean (NW Iberian Peninsula) from an area close to the record of SALVINI-PLAWEN (2008), but from a greater depth, 862 m (Table I). The description is consistent with the original (PRUVOT, 1891), although it presents some differences as regards the digestive system (Table II). Thus, the oesophagus shows a muscular sphincter, and the midgut bears serial constrictions along its entire length. As regards the radula, PRUVOT (1891) indicates that it has several middle denticles and SALVINI-PLAWEN (2008) describes a radula with two-three denticles. The specimens studied here bear a radula with four denticles as the figure of the original description shows (PRUVOT, 1891, pl. XXX, fig. 58). In addition, our specimens bear hollow acicular sclerites, arched, sigmoid and serrated in their distal end, which had not been previously described.

Two species of the genus *Pararrhopalia* are known so far: *Pararrhopalia pruvoti* from Banyuls-sur Mer (Mediterranean Sea) and the Atlantic Ocean (NW Iberian Peninsula) (PRUVOT, 1891; TODT, 2006; SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2008; this paper) and *Pararrhopalia fasciata* Salvini-Plawen,

1978 from South Shetland Islands (Antarctica) (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978). *Pararrhopalia oscari* n. sp. and *P. pruvoti* come from the same geographical region at a very similar depth and substratum (Table I). Both species have a very similar general configuration, but they present clear differences (Table II). *Pararrhopalia oscari* n. sp. has a radula with six middle denticles unlike *P. pruvoti* whose radula has four. The anterodorsal caecum of the midgut is unpaired in *Pararrhopalia oscari* n. sp., whereas that of *P. pruvoti* is paired. As regards the gonopericardial system, the new species has terminal pouches in the pericardium and seminal receptacles, both absent in *P. pruvoti*. The pallial cavity of *Pararrhopalia oscari* n. sp. is divided in two regions whereas in *P. pruvoti* it is simple. Although both species bear copulatory stylets accompanied by musculature along their entire length, only in *Pararrhopalia oscari* n. sp. the musculature forms a ventral pouch (PRUVOT, 1891; SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2008). In relation to *P. fasciata* (Table II), the radular teeth of *Pararrhopalia oscari* n. sp. have six middle denticles, unlike the three middle denticles of the radula of the Antarctic species. Besides the oesophagus of *Pararrhopalia oscari* n. sp. has a muscular sphincter absent in *P. fasciata*. There are also differences in the gonopericardial system. In *Pararrhopalia oscari* n. sp. the pericardium has three terminal pouches absent in *P. fasciata*. The spawning duct in *Pararrhopalia oscari* n. sp. has a couple of ventroanterior pouches absent in *P. fasciata*. The copulatory stylets of the new species occupy a longitudinal and ventral position to the spawning ducts, whereas in the Antarctic species, the stylets are transverse to the spawning ducts. These stylets are accompanied in both species by musculature along their entire length, but only in the new species the musculature form a ventral pouch (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978).

Also, the midgut with regular constrictions of *Pararrhopalia pruvoti* and *Pararrhopalia oscari* n. sp. have to led modify the diagnosis of the genus *Pararrhopalia*.

Table II. Comparison of the species of genus *Pararrhopalia* Simroth, 1893. Abbreviations: + present; - absent.

Tabla II. Comparación de las especies del género Pararrhopalia Simroth, 1893. Abreviaturas: + presente; - ausente.

	<i>P. pruvoti</i>	<i>P. fasciata</i>	<i>P. oscar</i> sp. nov.
Distribution	Mediterranean NW Iberian Peninsula	Antarctica	NW Iberian Peninsula
Depth (m)	80 - 862	220 - 240	438 - 459
Length (mm)	3.2 - 3.45	5	3.72 - 6.6
Cuticle (μm)	35 - 40	15	55 - 75
Epidermal papillae	+	+	+
Pedal folds	1	1	3
Anterodorsal misgut caecum	paired	not paired	not paired
Radular denticles	4	3	6
Oesophagus with sphincter	+	-	+
Pericardium pouches	-	-	+
Seminal vesicles	+	-	-
Seminal receptacles	-	+	+
Spawning duct pouches	+	-	+
Copulatory stylet position	longitudinal	transverse	longitudinal
Muscular pouch	-	-	+
Pallial cavity regions	-	-	2
Dorsoterminal sense organ	+	+	+

Genus *Pruvotina* Cockerell, 1903 (amended)

Type species: *Paramenia impexa* Pruvot, 1890.

With or without harpoon-shaped sclerites. Mouth opening (in part separated from atrium but) within common atrio-buccal opening. Distichous radula. Midgut

with regular constrictions. Secondary genital opening unpaired. Without copulatory stylets. With dorsoterminal sense organ. With respiratory folds.

Pruvotina glandulosa n. sp. (Figs. 2, 4, 7)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:7D27AF35-A489-42FE-BDD0-2695223A4E63

Type material (total 19 specimens, Table I). *Holotype*: SPAIN • 1 specimen in 5 μm cross-section serial cuts; 44° 11.652' N, 08° 58.152' W to 44° 11.539' N, 08° 57.574' W); 908-1106 m; A Selva 2008 station 7-DRN; bottom of sand with coral; Museo de Historia Natural of the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain) MHNUSC n° 10077. *Paratypes*: SPAIN • 1 specimen (paratype 1) in 5 μm cross-section serial cuts; same locality data as for holotype; Museo de Historia Natural of the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain) MHNUSC n° 10078 • 3 specimens (paratypes 2-4) in 5 μm cross-section serial cuts; same locality data as for holotype; collection of the Zoology and P.A. Department of the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain) • 1 specimen (paratype 5) in 2 μm cross-section serial cuts; same locality data as for holotype; Museo de Historia Natural of the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain) MHNUSC n° 10078 • 7 specimens (paratypes 6-12) preserved in 70% ethanol (70%); same locality data as for holotype; Museo de Historia Natural of the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain) MHNUSC n° 10078 • 6 specimens (paratypes 13-

18) preserved in 70% ethanol (70%); same locality data as for holotype; ; collection of the Zoology and P.A. Department of the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain).

Etymology: The specific name derives from Latin *glandula*: gland; *-osus*: rich. Regarding the large amount of glands the species has in its anterior body region.

Diagnosis: Thin cuticle without epidermal papillae. With six types of sclerites: one hook-shaped, four hollow acicular and one type of scale on the pedal groove. With three folds on the pedal groove not entering the pallial cavity. Atrial papillae simple or double. Glandular pharynx. Voluminous dorso-pharyngeal gland. Distichous radula. Radular teeth with distal hook, thin and pointed; two-three medial denticles. Ventrolateral foregut glands tubular, long and narrow (type A). Oesophagus long and narrow, surrounded by a glandular mass opening in the medial region of the midgut. With a short and unpaired anterodorsal midgut caecum. With seminal vesicles in the gonopericardioducts and pericardioducts. Unpaired genital orifice with glandular papilla opening in the ventroanterior pouch of the pallial cavity. Subterminal pallial cavity with a ventroanterior pouch. With four-six respiratory folds. With supra-pallial glands and two pairs of abdominal spicules. With a dorsoterminal sense organ.

Description: *Habitus:* Body 1.42 - 4.69 mm long and 0.31 - 0.52 mm wide (Fig. 2A). With sclerites projecting from the body, especially in the posterior part. Longitudinal pedal groove well-marked externally. Pallial cavity in subterminal position.

Mantle: Cuticle 20 - 40 μm thick, without epidermal papillae. Blad-shaped scales on the pedal groove (50 - 75 μm long, 15 - 20 μm wide) (Fig. 4C) and five types of hollow acicular sclerites: hook-shaped (85 - 145 μm long, 7.5 - 10 μm wide) with a tooth on the curvature (Fig.

4A); straight and narrow in two sizes: long (95 - 295 μm long, 5 μm wide), more abundant in medial and posterior regions, and short (45 - 65 μm long, 2.5 - 5 μm wide) more abundant in ventral region; sigmoid (65 - 155 μm long, 5.5 μm wide) with markedly curved proximal end; arched in the medial area (90 - 185 μm long, 2.5 - 5 μm wide) (Fig. 4B); serrated (105 - 155 μm long, 5 - 7.5 μm wide) curved in the distal end bearing four-six teeth, arranged all over the body, however, larger and more abundant in the anterior region.

Pedal groove and pallial cavity: Pedal pit (35 μm long, 45 μm high, 90 μm wide) densely ciliated. Pedal groove with three folds ending at the beginning of the pallial cavity. Anterior pedal glands well-developed. Subterminal pallial cavity bearing four-six short respiratory folds with wide base (50 μm long and up to 30 μm wide at the base) and a small ventroanterior pouch where the unpaired spawning duct opens (Fig. 7D, F). With supra-pallial glands within the respiratory folds and around the rectum (Fig. 7G). With two pairs of long acicular abdominal spicules (85 μm long, 5 μm wide) embedded in some invaginations located laterally to the pedal groove before the opening into the pallial cavity (Fig. 7D, F). These abdominal spicules has fibers of longitudinal musculature and associated glands.

Nervous system: Unpaired cerebral ganglion (45 μm long, 50 μm high, 100 μm wide) with oval transverse section with a pair of lateral ganglia innervating the atrium and the oral region. Large

(Right page) Figure 4. Optical microscope microphotographs of the types of sclerites. A-C: *Pruvotina glandulosa* n. sp. (A: hook-shaped with a tooth on the curvature; B: arched in the middle region; C: blade - shaped scales on the pedal groove); D-F: *Pruvotina bathyalis* sp.nov. (D: rectilinear long; E: sigmoid; F: excavated sclerite); G-I: *Pruvotina zamarroae* n. sp. (G: hook-shaped with a tooth on the curvature; H: sigmoid; I: serrated); J-L: *Pruvotina harpagone* n. sp. (J: harpoon-shaped distal end; K: hook-shaped with a tooth on the curvature; L: sigmoid).

Figure 4. Microfotografías al microscopio óptico de los tipos de escleritos. A-C: *Pruvotina glandulosa* n. sp. (A: forma de gancho con un diente en la curvatura; B: arqueado en la región media; C: escama en forma de cuchillo del surco pedio); D-F: *Pruvotina bathyalis* sp. nov. (D: largo rectilíneo; E: sigmoideo; F: esclerito excavado); G-I: *Pruvotina zamarroae* n. sp. (G: forma de gancho con un diente en la curvatura; H: sigmoideo; I: aserrado); J-L: *Pruvotina harpagone* n. sp. (J: forma de arpón en el extremo distal; K: forma de gancho con un diente en la curvatura; L: sigmoideo).

ventral ganglia (40 μm long, 35 μm high, 50 μm wide) joined by a large commissure. Buccal ganglion (15 μm long, 15 μm high, 20 μm wide) dorsally to the pharynx in the radular region (Fig. 7C, D). Wide suprarectal commissure (25 μm long, 10 μm wide) located dorsally to the rectum, at the level of the beginning of the pericardioducts (Fig. 7D).

Sense organs: Two types of papillae in the atrial cavity: simple and double, attached to the lateral and dorsal walls (Fig. 7A). Dorsoterminal sense organ well-developed (45 μm long, 45 μm high, 30 μm wide) in terminal position in the posterior region of the pallial cavity (Fig. 7D).

Digestive system: Atrium and mouth in a common indentation, functionally separated by a narrow septum with fibers of transverse musculature but without cuticle (Fig. 7D). Mouth bearing an anterior fold. It continues with a pharynx of oval section (135 μm long, 75 μm high, 105 μm wide) surrounded by a strong layer of musculature in the pre-radular region and numerous glands along its whole length. A dorso-pharyngeal gland (Fig. 7C, D) opens onto the radular region of the pharynx (45 μm long, 50 μm high, 100 μm wide). The radular apparatus comprises a distichous radula with five pairs of teeth and a radular sac (Fig. 7B, D). Radular teeth 21 μm long, very narrow in the medial area (3 μm wide) bearing a distal hook very thin and pointed and two-three small medial denticles (2 μm high, 1 μm wide) (Fig. 7B). Radular sac with circular section (20 μm long, 25 μm high, 40 μm wide) surrounded by a thin layer of longitudinal musculature (Fig. 7C). Ventrolateral foregut glands (Fig. 7C, D) tubular,

long and narrow (85 μm long, 10 - 20 μm high, 10 - 25 μm wide) type A (following SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ AND SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2007) or type *Pararrhopalia* (following HANDL AND TODT, 2005). They open laterally in the pharynx at the anterior region of the radular sac and run upwards to the posterior part of the body, reaching the midgut. Oesophagus with muscular sphincter, surrounded by a glandular mass (Fig. 7C, D). Midgut extending in an unpaired anterodorsal caecum (Fig. 7C, D), dorsoventrally flattened in variable lengths and sizes according to the specimens (55 - 80 μm long, 15 - 90 μm high, 130 - 150 μm wide). It also shows constrictions and serial lateral pouches along its whole length. Rectum of triangular section densely ciliated; it opens into the dorsoanterior wall of the pallial cavity posteriorly to the opening of the genital orifice (Fig. 7D, G).

Gonopericardial system: Each gonopericardioduct bears a voluminous seminal vesicle (65 μm long, 60 μm high, 55 μm wide) in its anterior region, loaded with spermatozoa (Fig. 7D, E). Heart (85 μm long, 10 - 15 μm high, 15 - 25 μm wide) attached to the dorsal wall of the pericardium (Fig. 7D), with an anterior ventricle, tubular of circular section and two bilobed posterior auricles. In the medial region of the pericardioducts, it has pair of small seminal vesicles (25 μm long, y 20 μm wide) (Fig. 7D) with spermatozoa. Anterior region of spawning ducts paired (45 μm long, 45 - 75 μm high, 50 - 70 μm wide). They fuse to form an only large duct (Fig. D, F) (90 μm long, 75 - 120 μm high, 165 - 200 μm wide) that open dorsally in the ventroanterior pouch of the pallial cavity through a glandular papilla.

(Right page) Figure 5. *Pararrhopalia pruvoti* Simroth, 1893. A-C, E, F: Microphotographs of the cross - sections of the body corresponding to lines 1, 2, 3, 4, 5. D: Anatomical reconstruction of the anterior and posterior body. G: Copulatory stylet. Abbreviations: at: atrium; bg: buccal ganglion; cg: cerebral ganglion; co: copulatory stylet; cu: cuticle; dc: anterodorsal caecum; dg: dorso-pharyngeal gland; go: gonad; gp: gonopericardioduct; he: heart; mg: midgut; mo: mouth; oe: oesophagus; pc: pallial cavity; pd: pericardioduct; ph: pharynx; pp: pedal pit; pr: pericardium; pso: pre - atrial sense organ; ra: radula; re: rectum; rs: radular sac; sc: suprarectal commissure; sd: spawning duct; spd: spawning duct pouch; sv: seminal vesicle; vfg: ventrolateral foregut glands.

Figura 5. *Pararrhopalia pruvoti* Simroth, 1893. A-C, E, F: Microfotografías de los cortes en sección correspondientes a las líneas 1, 2, 3, 4, 5. D: Reconstrucción anatómica de las partes anterior posterior. G: Estiletos copuladores. Abreviaturas: at: atrio; bg: ganglio bucal; cg: ganglio cerebral; co: estiletos copuladores; cu: cutícula; dc: ciego anterodorsal; dg: glándula dorsofaringea; go: gónada; gp: gonopericardioducto; he: corazón; mg: intestino; mo: boca; oe: esófago; pc: cavidad palea; pd: pericardioducto; ph: faringe; pp: fosa pedía; pr: pericardio; pso: órgano sensitivo preatrial; ra: rádula; re: recto; rs: saco radular; sc: comisura suprarrectal; sd: conducto de desove; spd: bolsa del conducto de desove; sv: vesícula seminal; vfg: glándulas ventrolaterales de la faringe.

Pruvotina bathyalis n. sp. (Figs. 2, 4, 8)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:6ADC2CF0-084E-4C65-8C52-05280E93F258

Type material (total 8 specimens, Table I). *Holotype*: SPAIN • 1 specimen cut in 5 µm cross sections; 44° 14.929' N, 08° 30.255' W to 44° 15.367' N, 08° 30.438' W; 2121-2516 m; bottom of large stones, polymetallic nodes and muddy sand with some coral; A Selva 2008 station 12-AT; Museo de Historia Natural of the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain) MHNUSC n° 10079. *Paratypes*: SPAIN • 1 specimen (paratype 1) cut in 5 µm cross sections; 44° 08.65' N, 08° 55.305' W to 44° 08.771' N, 08° 55.104' W; 566-581 m; bottom of dead corals at a depth; A Selva 2008 station 7-C; Museo de Historia Natural of the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain) MHNUSC n° 10080 • 1 developing juvenile specimen (paratype 2) cut in 5 µm cross sections; same locality data as paratype 1; collection of the Zoology and P.A. Department of the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain) • 1 specimen (paratype 3) cut in 5 µm cross sections; same locality data as paratype 1; Museo de Historia Natural of the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain) MHNUSC n° 10080 • 2 specimens (paratypes 4 and 5) cut in 5 µm cross sections; same locality data as paratype 1; collection of the Zoology and P.A. Department of the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain) • 1 specimen (paratype 6) preserved in 70% ethanol; same locality data as paratype 1; Museo de Historia Natural of the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain) MHNUSC n° 10080 • 1 specimen (paratype 7) preserved in 70% ethanol; same locality data as paratype 1; collection of the Zoology and P.A. Department of the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain)

Etymology: The specific name derives from Greek *bathos*:- depth. Latin *-ali*: belonging. Regarding the depth where the species was collected.

Diagnosis: Thick cuticle without epidermal papillae. With six types of sclerites: one hook-shaped, four hollow acicular and one scale-type on the pedal groove. With three folds on the pedal groove not entering the pallial cavity. Atrial papillae simple and double. Voluminous dorso-pharyngeal gland. Disticulous radula. Large radular teeth with a wide distal hook and five medial denticles. Ventrolateral foregut glands tubular, long and wide (type A). Muscular oesophagus long and narrow opening in the medial area of the midgut. With anterodorsal caecum of the midgut unpaired and short. Seminal vesicles in the gonopericardioducts and in the pericardioducts. Unpaired genital

orifice opening in the ventroanterior pouch of the pallial cavity. Terminal pallial cavity with two pouches. With 19 respiratory folds. With abdominal spicules. With a dorsoterminal sensitive organ.

Description: *Habitus:* Animals 2.14 - 3.8 mm long, 0.4 - 0.8 mm wide (Fig. 2B). No keels or crests. Sclerites protruding from the body in the posterior region. Pallial cavity in terminal position.

Mantle: Cuticle (40 - 100 µm thick) without epidermal papillae. Blade-shaped scales on the pedal groove (60 - 115 µm long, 5 - 15 µm wide) and five types of hollow acicular interwoven sclerites obliquely and radially inserted, arranged in three-four layers: hook-

(Right page) Figure 6. *Pararrhopalia oscari* n. sp. A-C, E-G: Microphotographs of the cross - sections of the body corresponding to lines 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6. D: Anatomical reconstruction of de anterior and posterior body. Abbreviations: *ap*: anterior region pallial cavity; *at*: atrium; *bg*: buccal ganglion; *cg*: cerebral ganglion; *co*: copulatory stylet; *com*: copulatory stylet musculature; *comp*: copulatory stylet musculature pouch; *cu*: cuticle; *dc*: anterodorsal caecum; *dg*: dorso-pharyngeal gland; *dso*: dorsoterminal sense organ; *gp*: gonopericardioduct; *mg*: midgut; *mo*: mouth; *oe*: oesophagus; *pc*: pallial cavity; *pd*: pericardioduct; *ph*: pharnx; *pp*: pedal pit; ; *ppc*: posterior region pallial cavity; *pr*: pericardium; *prp*: pericardium pouch; *ps*: pre - atrial sense organ; *ra*: radula; *re*: rectum; *rs*: radular sac; *sc*: suprarectal commissure; *sd*: spawning duct; *spd*: spawning duct pouch; *sr*: seminal receptacle; *vfg*: ventrolateral foregut glands; *vg*: ventral ganglion.

Figura 6. *Pararrhopalia oscaris* n. sp. A-C, E-G: Microfotografías de los cortes en sección correspondientes a las líneas 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6. D: Reconstrucción anatómica de las partes anterior posterior. Abreviaturas: ap: región anterior de la cavidad paleal; at: atrio; bg: ganglio bucal; cg: ganglio cerebral; co: estiletos copuladores; com: musculatura de los estiletos copuladores; comp: bolsa de la musculatura de los estiletos copuladores; cu: cutícula; dc: ciego anterodorsal; dg: glándula dorsofaríngea; dso: órgano sensitivo dorso-terminal; gp: gonopericardioducto; mg: intestino; mo: boca; oe: esófago; pc: cavidad paleal; pd: pericardioducto; ph: farínge; pp: fosa pedia; ppc: región posterior de la cavidad paleal; pr: pericardio; prp: bolsa del pericardio; pso: órgano sensitivo preatrial; ra: rádula; re: recto; rs: saco radular; sc: comisura supra-rectal; sd: conducto de desove; sdp: bolsa del conducto de desove; sr: receptáculo seminal; vfg: glándulas ventrolaterales de la farínge; vg: ganglio ventral.

shaped (95 - 238 μm long, 10 - 15 μm wide) with a tooth on the curvature; rectilinear and narrow in two sizes: long (90 - 225 μm long, 7.5 - 10 μm wide) more abundant in medial and posterior regions (Fig. 4D) and short (55 - 65 μm long, 7.5 μm wide) more abundant in ventral region; sigmoid (87 - 192 μm long, 5 - 7.5 μm wide) with very curved proximal end (Fig. 4E); arched in the medial region (75 - 163 μm long, 2.5 - 7.5 μm wide); serrated (100 - 130 μm long, 7.5 μm wide) curved in the distal end where they show four-six teeth, arranged all over the body, but larger and more abundant in the anterior region. The paratype 2 has small excavated sclerites (60 - 115 μm long, 5 μm wide) in the ventral region (Fig. 4F)

Pedal groove and pallial cavity: Pedal pit densely ciliated. Pedal groove with three folds ending at the beginning of the pallial cavity: a larger central one (50 μm high, up to 125 μm in paratype 1, 40 μm wide at the base) and two smaller lateral ones (25 μm high, 10 μm wide at the base). Paratype 2 bears three pedal folds in the anterior region and only one in the posterior region, which might be due to the specimen being immature. Voluminous pedal glands originating in the pedal pit and taking up almost the whole body cavity. Pallial cavity terminal with up to 19 respiratory folds (Fig. 8G), long with a wide base (125 μm long, up to 25 μm wide at the base) radially arranged on the lateral and dorsal walls. Cavity extending in two pouches (Fig. 8D, F): a dorsal pouch with remains of the respiratory folds which includes the rectum in its final section (50 μm long, 225 - 150 μm high, 225 - 125 μm wide) and a small ventral pouch (100 μm long, 75 - 100 μm high, 100 - 115 μm wide) where the spawning duct opens dorsally. With two groups of five large abdominal spicules (200 μm long, 12.5 μm wide each) (Fig. 8D, F); obliquely arranged with respect to the longitudinal axis of the animal; they are embedded in invaginations on both sides of the pedal groove before the beginning of the pallial cavity, with longitudinal musculature.

Nervous system: Unpaired cerebral ganglion very voluminous (120 μm long, 90 μm high, 170 μm wide) with oval cross section. Large pair of ventral ganglia (approximately 255 μm long, 250 μm high, 150 μm wide). Buccal ganglion of circular section (45 μm long, 35 μm wide) located on the radular region of the pharynx (Fig. 8C, D). Wide suprarectal commissure (35 μm long, 150 μm wide) located at the end of the seminal vesicles, dorsally to the rectum and anteriorly to the connection of the pericardioducts to the pericardium (Fig. 8D).

Sense organs: Simple papillae or papillae with two or more ramifications on the lateral and dorsal walls of the atrial cavity. With a well-developed dorso-terminal sense organ (75 μm long, 85 μm high, 100 μm wide) dorsally to the anterior region of the pallial cavity (Fig. 8D, F).

Digestive system: Atrium and mouth functionally separated by a septum with a thin layer of cuticle and fibers of transverse musculature (Fig. 8D). The mouth extends in a pharynx of oval-section (50 μm high, 125 μm wide) with a wide epithelial layer surrounded by longitudinal musculature. In the pre-radular region, the pharynx extends dorsally to join the voluminous dorso-pharyngeal gland (45 μm long, 125 μm high, 100 μm wide) (Fig. 8A, D). The radular apparatus comprises a distichous radula and a radular sac (Fig. 8B-D). Large radular teeth, approximately 37 μm long with a wide and curved distal hook as well as several medial denticles. Radular teeth bearing five small and pointed denticles, all equal in size, approximately 5 μm long and 1.5 μm wide at the base. Small radular sac (35 μm long, 40 μm high, 50 μm wide). Ventrolateral foregut glands (Fig. 8C, D) tubular, long and wide (195 μm long, 30 μm high, 40 μm wide) type A (following SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ AND SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2007) or type *Pararhopalia* (following HANDL AND TODT, 2005). They open laterally at the beginning of the radular sac. Long and wide oesophagus (160 μm long, 90 μm high,

70 μm wide) surrounded by thin layers of longitudinal musculature in its final section. It enters the midgut to open soon after in the medial region (Fig. 8D). The midgut extends anteriorly into a short unpaired anterodorsal caecum (Fig. 8C, D) reaching the radular region of the pharynx (60 μm long, 100 μm high, 180 μm wide). Midgut with serial lateral constrictions and lateral pouches along its entire length. The midgut narrows forming a small and densely ciliated rectum (40 μm wide) of circular section which opens in the dorsoanterior pouch of the pallial cavity (Fig. 8D), posteriorly to the outlet of the genital orifice.

Gonopericardial system: With globular seminal vesicles (125 μm high, 510 μm wide) in the gonopericardioducts, loaded with spermatozoa (Fig. 8D, E). Gonopericardioducts opening frontally in a large pericardium (330 μm long, 80 - 150 μm high, 50 - 200 μm wide). Heart (85 μm long, 10 - 15 μm high, 15 - 25 μm wide) within the pericardium attached to the dorsal wall (Fig. 8D). Paratype 2 bears oval blood cells, granulated and

nucleated, forming a large sinus dorsally to the atrium and surrounding the dorsoanterior pouch of the pallial cavity. Two long and narrow pericardioducts (430 μm long, 40 - 85 μm high, 45 - 30 μm wide) from the posterior end of the pericardium, curved towards the anterior region of the body, where they open on the dorsoterminal wall of the paired spawning duct (Fig. 8D). A pair of long and wide seminal vesicles stand out in the medial region of the pericardioducts (210 μm long, 200 μm wide) (Fig. 8D). Anterior region of spawning ducts paired (35 μm long, 135 μm high, 140 μm wide); it may perform the function of seminal receptacle due both to its structure and position and the presence of spermatozoa. Spawning ducts narrow in their medial section surrounded by a strong layer of musculature along their entire length. Posteriorly, they fuse in an only large duct (345 μm long, 400 μm high, 575 μm wide) sheathed in a cuticular layer, especially on the dorsal wall. Fused spawning duct open dorsally in the ventroanterior pouch of the pallial cavity (Fig. 8D).

Pruvotina zamarroae n. sp. (Figs. 2, 4, 9)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:8692B9E6-A41B-400D-A586-9E584F1B45A7

Type material (total 4 specimens, Table I). *Holotype:* SPAIN • 1 specimen in serial 5 μm cross-section cuts; 43° 56.478' N, 08° 54.199' W to 43° 55.934' N, 08° 54.849' W; 620-933 m; A Selva 2008 station 15-2-DRN; mud bottom with coral; Museo de Historia Natural of the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain) MHNUSC n° 10081. *Paratypes:* SPAIN • 1 specimen (paratype 1) in serial 5 μm cross-section cuts; 43° 48.421' N, 08° 51.453' W to 43° 49.160' N, 08° 51.091' W; 600 m; DIVA-Artabria I 2003 600-DRN; rocky bottom; Museo de Historia Natural of the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain) MHNUSC n° 10082 • 2 specimens (paratypes 2-3), juveniles with underdeveloped posterior region, in serial 5 μm cross-section cuts; 42° 51.20' N, 09° 43.85' W to 42° 52.97' N, 09° 44.25' W; 1177 - 1861 m; DIVA-Artabria II 2008 26-DRN-p; bottom of coral; collection of the Zoology and P.A. Department of the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain).

Etymology: The species is dedicated to Dr. María Zamarro Camino, specialist in the study of Solenogastres.

Diagnosis: Cuticle moderately thick without epidermal papillae. With six types of sclerites: one hook-shaped, four hollow acicular and one scale type on the pedal groove. With one fold on the pedal groove ending at the opening of the pallial cavity. Atrial papillae simple

and double. Small dorso-pharyngeal gland. Distichous radula. Radular teeth with narrow base, with acute distal hook very curved and three medial denticles in different sizes. Ventrolateral foregut glands tubular, sinuous and long (type A). Oesophagus opening in

the dorsal region of the midgut. With unpaired and short anterodorsal caecum of the midgut. With elongated seminal vesicles in the pericardioducts. Spawning duct very voluminous. Unpaired genital orifice opening in the ventral pouch of the pallial cavity. Terminal pallial cavity with a ventroanterior pouch. With eight respiratory folds. With abdominal spicules. With a dorso-terminal sense organ.

Description: Habitus: Animals 1.5 - 4.9 mm long, with expanded anterior region (diameter of anterior region 0.41 - 0.55 mm, diameter of posterior region 0.32 - 0.37 mm) (Fig. 2C). No keels or crest. Well-marked pedal groove. Opening of the pallial cavity in terminal position.

Mantle: Cuticle (35 - 65 μm thick) without epidermal papillae. Blade - shaped scales on the pedal groove (60 - 70 μm long, 15 - 20 μm largest diameter) and five types of hollow acicular sclerites obliquely inserted and radially arranged in three-five layers: hook-shaped (65 - 75 μm long, 7.5 - 10 μm wide) with a tooth on the curvature (Fig. 4G); rectilinear (80 - 185 μm long, 5 μm wide) more abundant in medial and posterior regions; sigmoid (85 - 105 μm long, 7.5 μm wide) with very curved proximal end (Fig. 4H); arched in the medial region: large (140 - 235 μm long, 10 μm wide) and small (55 - 120 μm long, 7.5 μm wide); serrated (75 - 110 μm long, 7.5 - 10 μm wide) curved in their distal end where four-six teeth are present (Fig. 4I), arranged along the entire body but larger and more abundant in the anterior region.

Pedal groove and pallial cavity: Large pedal pit (55 μm long, 100 μm high, 130 μm wide). Pedal groove with one fold (45 μm high, 15 μm wide) ending at the

opening of the pallial cavity. Anterior pedal glands well-developed taking up the entire anterior body region. Terminal pallial cavity with eight respiratory folds radially arranged, wide and short (Fig. 9G) (maximal length of 40 μm , up to 20 μm wide at the base). Pallial cavity extending anteriorly in a small ventral pouch where the unpaired genital orifice opens. Rectum opening in the dorsoanterior region of the pallial cavity. With abdominal spicules on both sides of the pedal groove before the opening of the pallial cavity (Fig. 9D), embedded in a pair of invaginations together with bundles of longitudinal musculature.

Nervous system: Unpaired cerebral ganglion (50 μm long, 70 μm high, 100 μm wide) with rectangular cross section, located dorsally to the radular region of the pharynx and posteriorly to the dorso-pharyngeal gland. Pair of ventral ganglia (25 μm long, 40 μm wide) arranged ventrally to the radular region (Fig. 9C, D). Small buccal ganglia (15 μm long, 15 μm high) dorsally to the posterior region of the oesophagus (Fig. 9D). Suprarrectal commissure long and wide (50 μm long, 10 μm wide) dorsally to the pericardium and anteriorly to the pericardioducts (Fig. 9D).

Sense organs: Atrial sense organ with simple and double papillae, attached to the lateral and dorsal walls of the atrial cavity. With a well-developed dorso-terminal sense organ (35 μm long, 40 μm high, 35 μm wide) dorsal to the pallial cavity (Fig. 9D).

Digestive system: Atrium and mouth in a common cavity, however functionally separated by a non - cuticularized wide groove with musculature. Mouth opening in the posterior region of the

(Right page) Figure 7. *Pruvotina glandulosa* n. sp. A-C, E-G: microphotographs of the cross - sections of the body corresponding to lines 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6; D: anatomical reconstruction of de anterior and posterior body. Abbreviations: *as*: abdominal spicules; *at*: atrium; *bg*: buccal ganglion; *cg*: cerebral ganglion; *cu*: cuticle; *dc*: anterodorsal caecum; *dg*: dorso-pharyngeal gland; *dso*: dorso-terminal sense organ; *go*: gonad; *gp*: gonopericardioduct; *he*: heart; *mg*: midgut; *mo*: mouth; *oe*: oesophagus; *pc*: pallial cavity; *pd*: pericardioduct; *pb*: pharnx; *pp*: pedal pit; *pr*: pericardium; *ra*: radula; *re*: rectum; *rf*: respiratory folds; *rs*: radular sac; *sc*: suprarrectal commissure; *sd*: spawning duct; *sg*: suprapallial glands; *sv*: seminal vesicle; *vfg*: ventrolateral foregut glands; *vg*: ventral ganglion; *vp*: ventral pouches.

Figura 7. Pruvotina glandulosa n. sp. A-C, E-G: Microfotografías de los cortes en sección correspondientes a las líneas 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6. D: Reconstrucción anatómica de las partes anterior posterior. Abreviaturas: as: espículas abdominales; at: atrio; bg: ganglio bucal; cg: ganglio cerebral; cu: cutícula; dc: ciego anterodorsal; dg: glándula dorsofaringea; dso: órgano sensitivo dorsoterminal; go: gónada; gp: gonopericardioducto; he: corazón; mg: intestino; mo: boca; oe: esófago; pc: cavidad paleal; pd: pericardioducto; ph: faringe; pp: fosa pedia; pr: pericardio; ra: rádula; re: recto; rf: pliegues respiratorios; rs: saco radular; sd: conducto de desove; sg: glándulas suprapaliales; sv: vesícula seminal; vfg: glándulas ventrolaterales de la faringe; vg: ganglio ventral; vp: bolsa ventral.

atrial cavity (Fig. 9D); it continues in the pharynx (65 μm high, 45 μm wide) with a high epithelium and surrounded by fibers of longitudinal musculature, forming a well-marked layer in the radular region. A small dorso-pharyngeal gland (25 μm long, 45 μm high, 55 μm wide) opens in the medial-dorsal region of the pharynx, anteriorly to the cerebral ganglion (Fig. 9D). The glandular cells associated to this dorso-pharyngeal gland reach the posterior region of the atrium. The medial-ventral region of the pharynx is also connected to the lateral body walls of the body by bundles of dorso-lateral musculature. Distichous radula with eight pairs of teeth. Teeth 25 μm long with narrow base (7 μm) and a very curved and acute distal hook. Each tooth bears three large medial denticles, with wide base, very separate (3 μm) in growing size from the base (Fig. 9B); the most distal denticle is the largest (4 μm high and 4 μm wide) at its base, whereas the other two smaller denticles are 3 μm high and 3 μm wide at their base. With radular sac (25 μm long, 40 μm high, 35 μm wide) surrounded by circular musculature (Fig. 9C). Ventrolateral foregut glands tubular, sinuous and very long (Fig. 9A, C, D), reaching the anterior region of the midgut (155 μm long, 20 μm wide), type A (following SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ AND SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2007) or type *Pararhopalia* (following HANDL AND TODT, 2005). They curve in their proximal end and open in the lateroventral region of the pharynx, anteriorly to the radular sac. Oesophagus long and moderately wide (50 μm long, 30 - 50 μm high, 50 - 65 μm wide), muscular, without associated glands. Midgut extends in a short

anterodorsal caecum reaching the radular region (Fig. 9A, C, D); it also shows constrictions and lateral pouches along its entire length. Long rectum, flattened in the posterior region (15 μm high, 40 μm wide) (Fig. 9D, F). Rectum of circular section opening in the dorsoanterior wall of the pallial cavity (Fig. 9D).

Gonopericardial system: Well-developed gonads with oocytes on the medial walls and spermatozoa on the lateral walls (except in paratypes 2 and 3 that are immature specimens). Pericardium voluminous in its anterior region (80 μm high, 75 μm wide) (Fig. 9E), however narrower in its posterior region (75 μm high, 15 μm wide) as it is dorsally displaced by the large unpaired spawning duct (Fig. 9D, F). Tubular heart of circular cross-section (115 μm long, 25 μm wide) (Fig. 9D-F) attached to the dorsal wall of the anterior region of the pericardium (it is detached anteriorly in paratype 1). Blood cells oval and nucleated grouped in large sinuses dorsally to the atrium, ventrally to the posterior region of the pericardium and within the respiratory folds. With a pair of seminal vesicles, cylindrical, long and narrow (50 μm long, 20 μm wide) (Fig. 9D, F) in the pericardioducts (185 μm long, 20 - 35 μm high, 15 - 35 μm wide). No sexual cells were observed in the seminal vesicles. All specimens lack seminal receptacles. Spawning duct paired in the anterior region (140 μm long, 105 μm high, 100 μm wide) fused posteriorly in an only duct of oval section (100 μm long, 100 μm high, maximum width of 160 μm), very voluminous, dorsally displacing the remaining structures (Fig. 9D, F). Genital orifice opening in the ventral pouch of the pallial cavity (Fig. 9D).

(Right page) Figure 8. *Pruvotina bathyalis* n. sp. A-C, E-G: Microphotographs of the cross - sections of the body corresponding to lines 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6. D: Anatomical reconstruction of de anterior and posterior body. Abbreviations: *as*: abdominal spicules; *at*: atrium; *bg*: buccal ganglion; *cg*: cerebral ganglion; *cu*: cuticle; *dc*: anterodorsal caecum; *dg*: dorso-pharyngeal gland; *dso*: dorsoterminal sense organ; *go*: gonad; *gp*: gonopericardioduct; *he*: heart; *mg*: midgut; *mo*: mouth; *oe*: oesophagus; *pc*: pallial cavity; *pd*: pericardioduct; *pb*: pharynx; *pp*: pedal pit; *pr*: pericardium; *ra*: radula; *re*: rectum; *rf*: respiratory folds; *rs*: radular sac; *sc*: suprarectal commissure; *sd*: spawning duct; *sv*: seminal vesicle; *vfg*: ventrolateral foregut glands; *vg*: ventral ganglion; *vp*: ventral pouch.

Figure 8. *Pruvotina bathyalis* n. sp. A-C, E-G: Microfotografías de los cortes en sección correspondientes a las líneas 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6. D: Reconstrucción anatómica de las partes anterior posterior. Abreviaturas: as: espículas abdominales; ar: atrio; bg: ganglio bucal; cg: ganglio cerebral; cu: cutícula; dc: ciego anterodorsal; dg: glándula dorsofaringea; dso: órgano sensitivo dorsoterminal; go: gónada; gp: gonopericardioducto; he: corazón; mg: intestino; mo: boca; oe: esófago; pc: cavidad paleal; pd: pericardioducto; ph: faringe; pp: fosa pedia; pr: pericardio; ra: rádula; re: recto; rf: pliegues respiratorios; rs: saco radular; sc: comisura suprarrectal; sd: conducto de desove; sv: vesícula seminal; vfg: glándulas ventrolaterales de la faringe; vg: ganglio ventral; vp: bolsa ventral.

Pruvotina harpagone n. sp. (Figs. 2, 4, 10)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:CB6DE147-B530-4CB1-B2A5-61E12990F435

Type material (total 3 specimens, Table I). *Holotype*: SPAIN • 1 specimen, cut in 5 μ m serial cross-sections; 42° 55.76' N, 09° 44.04' W to 42° 55.79' N, 09° 44.57' W; 709-728 m; DIVA-Artabria II 2008 25-EBS; rocky bottom; Museo de Historia Natural of the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain) MHNUSC n° 10083. *Paratypes*: SPAIN • 1 specimen (paratype 1), cut in 5 μ m serial cross-sections; same locality data as for the holotype; Museo de Historia Natural of the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain) MHNUSC n° 10084 • 1 specimen (paratype 2), cut in 5 μ m serial cross-sections; same locality data as for the holotype; collection of the Zoology and P.A. Department of the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain).

Etymology: The specific name derives from Latin harpago-: harpoon. Regarding the harpoon-shaped hollow acicular sclerites of this species.

Diagnosis: Thin cuticle without epidermal papillae. With six types of sclerites: one harpoon-shaped, one hook-shaped and four hollow acicular. With one fold in the pedal groove not entering the pallial cavity. Atrial papillae simple and ramified. Globular dorso-pharyngeal gland. Distichous radula. Radular teeth with distal hook and at least three medial denticles. of ventrolateral foregut glands with a narrow duct surrounded by a large glandular mass (type A). Oesophagus opening in the medial region of the midgut. With anterodorsal caecum of the midgut paired in its anterior region. Seminal vesicles in the pericardioducts. Genital orifice unpaired opening in the ventroanterior wall of the pallial cavity. Terminal pallial cavity with a dorsoanterior pouch. With 12 - 14 respiratory folds. With abdominal spicules. With a dorso-terminal sense organ.

Description: *Habitus*: Animals 2.25 - 3.12 mm long, 0.42 - 0.65 mm wide (Fig. 2D). Without keels or crests. Sclerites very long, protruding widely from the body, thus giving the specimens a

bristly appearance. Longitudinal pedal groove well-marked. Pallial cavity in terminal position.

Mantle: Thin cuticle (20 - 25 μ m thick) without epidermal papillae. With six types of hollow acicular sclerites obliquely inserted and radially arranged in three-five layers: with harpoon-shaped distal end (375 μ m long, 8.75 μ m wide) (Fig. 4J); hook-shaped (100 - 440 μ m long, 5 - 20 μ m wide) with a tooth on the curvature (Fig. 4K); rectilinear (200 - 600 μ m long, 5 - 15 μ m wide). Sigmoid (87.7 μ m long, 5 μ m wide) very scarce (Fig. 4L); arched in the medial region (150 - 325 μ m long, 5 - 10 μ m wide); serrated (175 - 412 μ m long, 5 - 15 μ m wide) curved in the distal end with up to 10 teeth, arranged throughout the entire body, however larger and more abundant in the anterior region. No scales on the pedal groove were observed.

Pedal groove and pallial cavity: Pedal pit (60 μ m long, 50 μ m high, 160 μ m wide) densely ciliated. Pedal groove with a wide pedal fold (40 μ m high, 45 μ m wide) not entering the pallial cavity. With voluminous anterior pedal glands.

(Right page) Figure 9. *Pruvotina zamarroae* n. sp. A-C, E-G: Microphotographs of the cross - sections of the body corresponding to lines 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6. D: Anatomical reconstruction of de anterior and posterior body. Abbreviations: *as*: abdominal spicules; *at*: atrium; *bg*: buccal ganglion; *cg*: cerebral ganglion; *cu*: cuticle; *dc*: anterodorsal caecum; *dg*: dorso-pharyngeal gland; *dso*: dorso-terminal sense organ; *go*: gonad; *he*: heart; *mg*: midgut; *mo*: mouth; *oe*: oesophagus; *pc*: pallial cavity; *pd*: pericardioduct; *ph*: pharinx; *pp*: pedal pit; *pr*: pericardium; *ra*: radula; *re*: rectum; *rf*: respiratory folds; *rs*: radular sac; *sc*: suprarectal commissure; *sd*: spawning duct; *sv*: seminal vesicle; *vfg*: ventro-lateral foregut glands; *vg*: ventral ganglion; *vp*: ventral pouch.

Figure 9. *Pruvotina zamorroae* n. sp. A-C, E-G: Microfotografías de los cortes en sección correspondientes a las líneas 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6. D: Reconstrucción anatómica de las partes anterior posterior. Abreviaturas: as: espículas abdominales; at: atrio; bg: ganglio bucal; cg: ganglio cerebral; cu: cutícula; dc: ciego anterodorsal; dg: glándula dorsofaringea; dso: órgano sensitivo dorsoterminal; go: gónada; he: corazón; mg: intestino; mo: boca; oe: esófago; pc: cavidad paleal; pd: pericardioducto; ph: faringe; pp: fosa pedia; pr: pericardio; ra: rádula; re: recto; rf: pliegues respiratorios; rs: saco radular; sc: comisura suprarrectal; sd: conducto de desove; sv: vesícula seminal; vfg: glándulas ventrolaterales de la faringe; vg: ganglio ventral; vp: bolsa ventral.

Terminal pallial cavity with 12 - 14 long respiratory folds with wide base (75 μm long, up to 20 μm wide at the base) (Fig. 10C). Dorsoanterior region of the pallial cavity extending anteriorly in a small pouch (35 μm long, 105 μm high, 240 μm wide) where the rectum opens (Fig. 10D). Ventral groove of the spawning duct opening in the ventroanterior wall. With abdominal spicules (Fig. 10C, D).

Nervous system: Unpaired cerebral ganglion (120 μm long, 60 μm high, 160 μm wide) of oval cross-section, anteriorly to the dorso-pharyngeal gland. Buccal ganglia in dorsal position at the beginning of the radular region. No lateral ganglia or suprarectal commissure observed.

Sense organs: Atrial papillae simple and with two or three ramifications attached to the lateral and dorsal walls of the atrial cavity. Dorsoterminal sense organ well-developed (55 μm long, 35 μm high, 45 μm wide) in dorsal position in the posterior region of the pallial cavity (Fig. 10C, D).

Digestive system: Atrium and mouth in a common cavity (Fig. 10D), however functionally separated by a non-cuticularized narrow septum with fibers of transverse musculature. Mouth continues in a pharynx of high epithelium slightly folded and surrounded by a fiber wrap of circular musculature (210 μm long, 135 - 60 μm high, 130 - 100 μm wide). A small and globular dorso-pharyngeal gland (30 μm long, 50 μm high, 35 μm wide) opens in the radular region of the pharynx, posteriorly to the cerebral ganglion (Fig. 10A, D). Distichous radula with teeth. Teeth typical of the genus *Pruvotina*, with a protruding distal hook and at least 3 medial denticles, very small and difficult to observe. Small radular sac (40 μm long, 45 μm high, 35 μm wide) surrounded by a thin muscular wrap. Ventrolateral foregut glands type A (following SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ AND SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2007) or type *Pararhopalia* (following HANDL AND TODT, 2005) (Fig. 10B, D), formed by a narrow duct surrounded by a large glandular mass (100 - 75 μm high, 50 - 60 μm

wide) and opening laterally in the radular region, not reaching the midgut (70 μm long). Oesophagus (35 μm long, 75 - 40 μm high, 50 - 30 μm wide) with high folded epithelium surrounded by a layer of circular musculature. Midgut extending in a paired anterodorsal caecum (155 μm long, 80 - 60 μm high, 250 - 125 μm wide) (Fig. 10B, D), that reaches the radular region, and with serial lateral constrictions and lateral pouches along its entire length. Rectum opening in the dorsoanterior pouch of the pallial cavity (Fig. 10D).

Gonopericardial system: Gonads with oocytes. With small seminal vesicles in the medial region of the pericardioducts (Fig. 10D). Anterior region of spawning ducts paired, fusing posteriorly to form an only large duct. Genital orifice opening in the ventral wall of the pallial cavity through a ventral groove, still open in its dorsal region.

Taxonomical discussion: The four new species of *Pruvotina* described in this paper differ from the 10 Antarctic and subantarctic species of the genus in their geographical distribution as well as in important morphological features (Table III). Thus, the new species lack the brood chamber observed in *P. providens*, *P. praegnans*, and *P. uniperata*; they show no seminal receptacles present in *P. megathecata*, *P. pallioglandulata*, *P. longispinosa*, *P. peniculata*, *P. gauzi* and *P. manifesta*, however, they bear abdominal spicules and supra-pallial glands absent in *P. cryophila*. This species is the most to like the species described herein (PELSENEER, 1901; THIELE, 1913; SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978; ZAMARRO ET AL., 2013).

As for the two European species of the genus: *P. impexa* was described from western Mediterranean, but a depth of only 80 m. (PRUVOT, 1890, 1891; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ ET AL., 2014), whereas *P. artabra* was described in the same geographical area and at similar bathymetry as the four new species of *Pruvotina* (ZAMARRO ET AL., 2013; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ ET AL., 2014). Nevertheless, important differences have been observed between the new species and these two European species (Table II).

Figure 10. *Pruvotina harpagone* n. sp. A-C: Microphotographs of the cross - sections of the body corresponding to lines 1, 2, 3. D: Anatomical reconstruction of the anterior and posterior body. Abbreviations: *as*: abdominal spicules; *at*: atrium; *cg*: cerebral ganglion; *cu*: cuticle; *dc*: anterodorsal caecum; *dg*: dorso-pharyngeal gland; *dp*: dorsal pouch; *dso*: dorsoterminal sense organ; *go*: gonad; *mg*: midgut; *mo*: mouth; *oe*: oesophagus; *pc*: pallial cavity; *pd*: pericardioduct; *ph*: pharynx; *pp*: pedal pit; *pr*: pericardium; *ra*: radula; *re*: rectum; *rf*: respiratory folds; *rs*: radular sac; *sd*: spawning duct; *sv*: seminal vesicle; *vfg*: ventrolateral foregut glands.

Figure 10. *Pruvotina harpagone* n. sp. A-C: Microfotografías de los cortes en sección correspondientes a las líneas 1, 2, 3. D: Reconstrucción anatómica de las partes anterior posterior. Abreviaturas: *as*: espículas abdominales; *at*: atrio; *cg*: ganglio cerebral; *cu*: cutícula; *dc*: ciego anterodorsal; *dg*: glándula dorsofaringea; *dp*: bolsa dorsal; *dso*: órgano sensitivo dorsoterminal; *go*: gónada; *mg*: intestino; *mo*: boca; *oe*: esófago; *pc*: cavidad paleal; *pd*: pericardioducto; *ph*: faringe; *pp*: fosa pedia; *pr*: pericardio; *ra*: rádula; *re*: recto; *rf*: pliegues respiratorios; *rs*: saco radular; *sd*: conducto de desove; *sv*: vesícula seminal; *vfg*: glándula ventrolaterales de la faringe.

P. glandulosa n. sp. differs from *P. impexa*, among other characters (Table III), because it has four to six respiratory folds, a sphincter in the oesophagus, abdominal spicules, supra-pallial glands and terminal pallial cavity with a ven-

troanterior pouch (PRUVOT, 1890, 1891; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ *ET AL.*, 2014). In relation to *P. artabra*, *P. glandulosa* n. sp. (Table III) bears four to six respiratory folds, radular teeth with two-three medial denticles, a glandular oesopha-

Table III. Comparison of the species of de genus *Pruvotina* Cockerell, 1903. Abbreviations: + present; - absent; ? unknown; *gp* gonopericardioduct; *pd* pericardioduct.

	<i>P. impexa</i>	<i>P. cryophila</i>	<i>P. providens</i>	<i>P. gounzi</i>	<i>P. longispinosq</i>	<i>P. megantheana</i>	<i>P. palliogambulata</i>
Distribution	Mediterranean	Antarctica	Antarctica	Antarctica	Antarctica	South America	Antarctica
Depth (m)	60 - 80	342 - 550	385	385	64 - 220 (3890?)	118 - 903	210 - 220
Length (mm)	12	2,1	8,5	?	5	5	5
Harpoon	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Dorsal crest	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Cuticle (µm)	?	40 - 70	110 - 130	20 - 40	60 - 80	60 - 80	35 - 70
Epidermal papillae	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
Pedal folds	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Anterodorsal caecum	not paired	not paired	not paired	?	not paired	not paired	not paired
Radular denticles	3	4	3 - 4	?	4	3 - 4	4
Oesophagus	-	-	+	?	+	+	-
Midgut sphincter	-	-	-	?	-	-	-
Seminal vesicles	pd	?	-	pd	-	-	-
Seminal receptacles	-	?	-	+	+	+	+
Abdominal spicules	-	+	-	-	+	+	-
Supra-pallial glands	-	-	-	+	-	+	+
Pallial cavity pouches	-	-	ventral	ventral	-	dorsal	-
Incubatrix camera	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
Respiratory folds	12 - 20	2 - 3	13	7	20	30	8 - 10

gus, and abdominal spicules, whereas it lacks abdominal sphincters, seminal receptacles and a dorsoanterior pouch in the pallial cavity (ZAMARRO ET AL., 2013; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ ET AL., 2014).

P. bathyalis n. sp. has, in contrast with *P. impexa*: a radula with more denticles, the oesophagus with sphincter, the pallial cavity with pouches, and abdominal spicules (PRUVOT, 1980, 1981; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ ET AL., 2014) (Table III). *P. bathyalis* n. sp. differs from *P. artabra*, among other characters, in (Table III) the fact it has a radular teeth with more denticles, a muscular oesophagus, abdominal spicules and lacks seminal

receptacles (ZAMARRO ET AL., 2013; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ ET AL., 2014).

P. zamarroae n. sp. differs from *P. impexa* in (Table III): an oesophagus with sphincter, abdominal spicules and pallial cavity with 8 respiratory folds and a ventroanterior pouch (PRUVOT, 1980, 1981; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ ET AL., 2014). In contrast with *P. artabra*, *P. zamarroae* n. sp. bears (Table III): radular teeth with three denticles in different sizes, a oesophagus with sphincter, abdominal spicules and, a terminal pallial cavity with eight respiratory folds and dorsoanterior pouch, whereas it lacks sphincters in the midgut and

Tabla III. Comparación de las especies del género *Pruvotina* Cockerell, 1903. Abreviaturas: + presente; - ausente; ? desconocido; gp gonopericardioducto; pd pericardioducto.

<i>P. peniculata</i>	<i>P. propegnans</i>	<i>P. unipapata</i>	<i>P. artabra</i>	<i>P. rmanista</i>	<i>P. glandulosa</i> n. sp.	<i>P. bathyatis</i> n. sp.	<i>P. zammaroae</i> n. sp.	<i>P. harpagone</i> n. sp.
South America	Antarctica	Antarctica	NW Iberian Peninsula	Antarctica	NW Iberian Peninsula	NW Iberian Peninsula	NW Iberian Peninsula	NW Iberian Peninsula
119 - 549	148 - 220	210 - 2306	788 - 1191	254	908 - 1106	566 - 2516	600 - 1861	709 - 728
4	6	4	3 - 2	3	1.42 - 4.69	2.14 - 3.8	1.5 - 4 - 9	2.25 - 3.12
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+
+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
40 - 60	60 - 160	75 - 100	35 - 50	30 - 40	20 - 40	40 - 100	35 - 65	20 - 25
+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-
1	1	1	1	1	3	3	1	1
paired	not paired	not paired	paired	paired	not paired	not paired	impair	pair
3 - 5	3 - 4	4	4	5	2 - 3	5	3	3
+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+
+	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
-	-	-	gp	gp	gp/pd	pd	pd	pd
+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-
+	-	+	-	-	+	+	+	+
+	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	-
ventral	ventral	-	dorsal/ventral	-	ventral	dorsal/ventral	ventral	dorsal
-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
3 - 5	28	10	14	10	4 - 6	19	8	12 - 14

seminal receptacles (ZAMARRO *ET AL.*, 2013; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ *ET AL.*, 2014).

P. harpagone n. sp. is the only species of the genus *Pruvotina* that has harpoon-shaped sclerites; this sclerite type was only known for species of the genus *Uncimienia* Nierstrasz, 1903 and *Unciherpia* García-Álvarez, Salvini-Plawen and Urgorri, 2001 (subfamily Unciherpiinae García-Álvarez, Salvini-Plawen and Urgorri, 2001) (GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ AND SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2007). *P. harpagone* n. sp. differs from *P. impexa* (Table III): an oesophagus with sphincter, a paired anterodorsal caecum of the midgut, abdominal spicules, and

a pallial cavity with dorsoanterior pouch (PRUVOT, 1980, 1981; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ *ET AL.*, 2014). With respect to *P. artabra*, *P. harpagone* n. sp. differs in (Table III): bearing an oesophagus with a sphincter, abdominal spicules, having a terminal pallial cavity with eight respiratory folds and dorsoanterior pouch, and lacking sphincters in the midgut and seminal receptacles (ZAMARRO *ET AL.*, 2013; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ *ET AL.*, 2014).

Also, the harpoon-shaped sclerites of *Pruvotina harpagone* n. sp. have led to modify the diagnosis of the genus *Pruvotina*, *Pararrhopalia* and *Labidoherpia*.

Genus *Labidoherpia* Salvini-Plawen, 1978 (amended)

Type species: *Pruvotina spinosa* Thiele, 1913.

Without harpoon-shaped sclerites.
Mouth opening within common atrio-
buccal opening. Distichous radula.
Midgut with regular constrictions.

Secondary genital opening unpaired.
With copulatory stylets. With dorsoter-
minal sense organ. With respiratory
folds.

Labidoherpia vitucoi Pedrouzo and García-Álvarez n. sp. (Figs. 1, 3, 11)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:CAF0DBD5-1777-4600-A12D-C02522178F4D

Type material (total 2 specimens, Table I). *Holotype*: SPAIN • 1 specimen cut in 5 µm serial cross-sections; 44° 09.896' N, 08° 39.581' W to 44° 10.129' N, 08° 39.494' W; 438-459 m; A Selva 2008 11-DRN; bottom of polymetallic nodules with slightly muddy sand; Museo de Historia Natural of the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain) MHNUSC n° 10085 *Paratype*: SPAIN • 1 specimen (paratype 1) cut in 5 µm serial cross-sections; same locality data as for holotype; collection of the Zoology and P.A. Department of the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain).

Etymology: The species is dedicated to Prof. Dr. Victoriano Urgorri, malacologist and director of the DIVA-Artabria and A Selva expeditions.

Diagnosis: Moderately thick cuticle without epidermal papillae. With six types of sclerites: one hook-shaped, four types of hollow acicular and one scale on the pedal groove. With three pedal folds not entering the pallial cavity. Atrial papillae single, double, and triple. With dorsal gland. Distichous radula. Teeth with an acute distal hook and six middle denticles. Ventrolateral foregut glands tubular and narrow (type A). Oesophagus with muscular sphincter. With unpaired anterodorsal caecum of the midgut. With seminal receptacles. Spawning duct with a couple of ventro-posterior pouches. Unpaired genital orifice opening into the dorsal wall of the pallial cavity through a sphincter. Ventral pallial cavity without pouches.

With eight-nine respiratory folds. With a pair of bundles of copulatory stylets. With a dorsoterminal sense organ.

Description: *Habitus*: *Holotype* 5.62 mm long and 0.65 mm wide; *paratype* 1 3.68 mm long and 0.5 mm wide (Fig. 1C). No keels or crests. Well-marked pedal groove externally. Opening of the pallial cavity in ventral position.

Mantle: Cuticle (50 - 70 µm thick) without epidermal papillae. Blade-shaped scales in the pedal groove (75 - 100 µm long, 10 - 12.5 µm in largest diameter) (Fig. 3I) and five types of hollow acicular sclerites with tangential and radial insertion arranged in four layers: hook-shaped (100 - 167.5 µm long, 10 µm wide) with a tooth on the curvature (Fig. 3G); rectilinear (75 - 100

(Right page) Figure 11. *Labidoherpia vitucoi* n. sp. A-C, E-G: Microphotographs of the cross - sections of the body corresponding to lines 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6. D: Anatomical reconstruction of de anterior and posterior body. Abbreviations: *at*: atrium; *bg*: buccal ganglion; *cg*: cerebral ganglion; *co*: copulatory stylet; *com*: copulatory stylet musculature; *comp*: copulatory stylet musculature pouch; *cu*: cuticle; *dc*: anterodorsal caecum; *dg*: dorso-pharyngeal gland; *dso*: dorsoterminal sense organ; *he*: heart; *mg*: midgut; *mo*: mouth; *oe*: oesophagus; *pc*: pallial cavity; *pd*: pericardioduct; *ph*: pharnx; *pp*: pedal pit; *pr*: pericardium; *ra*: radula; *re*: rectum; *rf*: respiratory folds; *rs*: radular sac; *sc*: supra-rectal commissure; *sd*: spawning duct; *spd*: spawning duct pouch; *sr*: seminal receptacle; *sv*: seminal vesicle; *vfg*: ventrolateral foregut glands; *vg*: ventral ganglion.

Figure 11. *Lavidotherpia vitucoi* n. sp. A-C, E-G: Microfotografías de los cortes en sección correspondientes a las líneas 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6. D: Reconstrucción anatómica de las partes anterior posterior. Abreviaturas: at: atrio; bg: ganglio bucal; cg: ganglio cerebral; co: estiletes copuladores; com: musculatura de los estiletes copuladores; comp: bolsa de la musculatura de los estiletes copuladores; cu: cutícula; dc: ciego anterodorsal; dg: glándula dorsofaríngea; dso: órgano sensitivo dorsoterminal; he: corazón; mg: intestino; mo: boca; oe: esófago; pc: cavidad pleal; pd: pericardioducto; ph: farínge; pp: fosa pedía; pr: pericardio; ra: rádula; re: recto; rf: pliegues respiratorios; rs: saco radular; sc: comisura suprarrectal; sd: conducto de desove; spd: bolsa del conducto de desove; sr: receptáculo seminal; sv: vesícula seminal; vfg: glándulas ventrolaterales de la farínge; vg: ganglio ventral.

μm long, 10 - 12 μm wide); sigmoid (100 - 180 μm long, 7.5 - 10 μm wide) (Fig. 3H); serrated (100 μm long, 2.5 - 10 μm wide) in the anterior region.

Pedal groove and pallial cavity: Pedal pit with ciliated epithelium (95 μm long, 125 μm high, 150 μm wide). Pedal groove with three folds; one large central fold (40 - 50 μm high, 45 μm wide) and two smaller lateral folds (15 - 20 μm high, 5 - 10 μm wide) ending at the opening of the pallial cavity. Well-developed anterior pedal glands occupying the entire anterior body region. Ventral pallial cavity with eight-nine respiratory folds, radially arranged, wide and long (maximum length of 65 μm and up to 30 μm wide at the base) (Fig. 11G).

Nervous system: Unpaired cerebral ganglion with oval cross-section (135 μm long, 90 μm high, 80 μm wide) (Fig. 11A-D). The pair of ventral ganglia (45 μm long, 50 μm wide) are arranged ventrally to the radular region. Small buccal ganglia (25 μm wide) dorsal to the posterior region of the oesophagus. Long and wide suprarectal commissure (50 μm long, 15 μm wide) in the posterior region of the seminal receptacles (Fig. 11D).

Sense organs: Atrial sense organ with branched papillae attached to the lateral and dorsal walls of the atrial cavity. With a well-developed dorsoterminal sense organ (30 μm long, 50 μm high, 40 μm wide) in terminal position (Fig. 11D).

Digestive system: Atrium and mouth in a common cavity, but functionally separated by a broad, non-cuticularized groove with musculature. Long and wide pharynx (200 μm long, 125 μm high, 135 μm wide) surrounded by a

thin muscular layer. A large dorso-pharyngeal gland (90 μm long, 15 μm high, 60 μm wide) opens into the pre-radular region of the pharynx (Fig. 11A, D). Radular apparatus consisting of a distichous radula and a radular sac (Fig. 11B-D). The teeth bear a sharp and very curved distal hook (10 μm). Each tooth has six-seven long middle denticles (4 μm high, 1.5 μm wide at the base) (Fig. 11C). With a radular sac (170 μm long, 40 μm high, 50 μm wide) surrounded by circular musculature. Ventrolateral foregut glands tubular and narrow (80 μm long, 30 μm high, 20 μm wide), type A (following SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ AND SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2007) or type *Pararrhopalia* (following HANDL AND TODT, 2005) (Fig. 11C, D). They open into the lateroventral region of the pharynx, anteriorly to the radular sac and then run posteriorly until reaching the midgut. Muscular oesophagus long and narrow (110 μm long, 50 μm high, 75 μm wide) (Fig. 11C, D). The midgut extends in an unpaired anterodorsal caecum that reaches the radular region (Fig. 11C, D); it also has constrictions and lateral pouches along its entire length. Narrow rectum opening dorsally in the pallial cavity (Fig. 11D, F).

Gonopericardial system: Highly developed gonads with oocytes in the posterior region. With a large blood sinus in the dorsal region of the atrium, with oval and nucleated blood cells. Long and narrow pericardium (235 μm long, 35 μm high, 65 μm wide) with the heart attached to its dorsal wall (Fig. 11D-F). Long and narrow seminal receptacles (110 μm long, 15 μm high, 20 μm wide) observed at the connection of the peri-

(Right page) figure 12. *Lavidoberpia lucus* n. sp. A-C, E-G: Microphotographs of the cross - sections of the body corresponding to lines 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6. D: Anatomical reconstruction of de anterior and posterior body. Abbreviations: *at*: atrium; *bg*: buccal ganglion; *cg*: cerebral ganglion; *co*: copulatory stylet; *com*: copulatory stylet musculature; *cu*: cuticle; *dg*: dorso-pharyngeal gland; *he*: heart; *mg*: midgut; *mo*: mouth; *musc*: musculature; *oe*: oesophagus; *pc*: pallial cavity; *pd*: pericardioduct; *pg*: pedal gland; *ph*: pharnx; *pp*: pedal pit; *pr*: pericardium; *prp*: pericardium pouch; *ra*: radula; *re*: rectum; *rf*: respiratory folds; *rs*: radular sac; *sc*: suprarectal commissure; *sd*: spawning duct; *spd*: spawning duct pouch; *sr*: seminal receptacle; *vfg*: ventrolateral foregut glands.

Figure 12. *Lavidotherpia lucus* n. sp. A-C, E-G: Microfotografías de los cortes en sección correspondientes a las líneas 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6. D: Reconstrucción anatómica de las partes anterior posterior. Abreviaturas: at: atrio; bg: ganglio bucal; cg: ganglio cerebral; co: estiletes copuladores; com: musculatura de los estiletes copuladores; cu: cutícula; dg: glándula dorsofaringea; he: corazón; mg: intestino; mo: boca; oe: esófago; pc: cavidad paleal; pd: pericardioducto; pg: glándula pedia; ph: faringe; pp: fosa pedia; pr: pericardio; prp: bolsa del pericardio; ra: rádula; re: recto; rf: pliegues respiratorios; rs: saco radular; sc: comisura suprarrectal; sd: conducto de desove; spd: bolsa del conducto de desove; sr: receptáculo seminal; vfg: glándulas ventrolaterales de la faringe.

cardioducts with the spawning duct (Fig. 11D-F). The spawning duct has a three-lobed appearance due to the pouches located on its ventroposterior wall. The genital orifice opens through a weak sphincter in the dorso-anterior region of the pallial cavity. This species bears 2 bundles of copulatory stylets

(285 μm long, 50 μm high, 40 μm wide) running from the gonopericardioducts to the opening of the pallial cavity (Fig. 11D-F). The entire length of the stylets is surrounded by musculature. At the posterior end, the musculature forms a pouch that does not open to the outside (Fig. 11D, F).

Labidoherpia lucus n. sp. (Figs. 1, 3, 12)

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:A6C07018-6DD8-4B36-94FB-20F1137038C6

Type material. *Holotype*: SPAIN • 1 specimen (Table I) cut in 5 μm serial cross-sections; 43° 48.514' N, 08° 51.439' W to 43° 49.163' N, 08° 51.157' W; 616 m; DIVA Artabria I 2003 600-AT; rocky bottom; Museo de Historia Natural of the University of Santiago de Compostela (Spain) MHNUSC n° 10086. **Etymology:** The species is dedicated to the author's hometown: Lugo, *Lucus Augusti*.

Diagnosis: Thin cuticle without epidermal papillae. With five types of sclerites: one hook-shaped, three hollow acicular and one scale of the pedal groove. With three pedal folds not entering the pallial cavity. Double and triple atrial papillae. With a dorsal gland. Disticulous radula. Teeth with a distal hook and three middle denticles. Ventrolateral foregut glands tubular and narrow (type A). Oesophagus with muscular sphincter. Without anterodorsal caecum of the midgut. Pericardium with a posterior pouch. With small seminal receptacles. Spawning duct with a pair of ventrolateral pouches. Unpaired genital orifice. Ventral pallial cavity with a ventral pouch. With four-six respiratory folds. With two bundles of 12-15 copulatory stylets. No dorsoterminal sense organ was observed.

Description: *Habitus:* Animal 3 mm long and 0.375 mm wide (Fig. 1D). Without keels or crests. Sclerites projecting from the body, especially in the anterior region. Longitudinal pedal groove well-marked externally. Opening of the pallial cavity in ventral position.

Mantle: Thin cuticle (25 - 35 μm thick) without epidermal papillae. Blade-shaped scales in the pedal groove (50 μm long, 12.5 μm maximum wide) and four types of hollow acicular sclerites with tangential and radial insertion arranged in four layers: hook-shaped

(75 - 125 μm long, 5 - 7.5 μm wide) with a tooth on the curvature (Fig. 3J); rectilinear in two sizes: small and wide (62.5 - 112.5 μm long, 5 - 7 μm wide), long and narrow (125 μm long, 2.5 μm wide) located in the ventral region (Fig. 3K); sigmoid (82.5 - 137.5 μm long, 5 - 10 μm wide) very scarce; arched in the middle region (62.5 - 162 μm long, 5 - 10 μm wide) (Fig. 3L).

Pedal groove and pallial cavity: Pedal pit (95 μm long, 80 μm high, 115 μm wide) densely ciliated. Pedal groove with three pedal folds not entering the pallial cavity: one large central fold (35 μm high, 20 μm wide) and two smaller lateral folds (10 - 12.5 μm high, 7.5 μm wide). A pair of voluminous pedal glands (45 μm long, 75 μm high, 85 μm wide) come out from the pedal pit. Small pallial cavity and ventral opening with four-six short, broad-based respiratory folds (20 μm long and up to 20 μm wide at the base) (Fig. 12G). The ventroanterior region of the pallial cavity extends anteriorly in a small pouch (25 μm long, 25 μm high, 35 μm wide) where the genital orifice opens (Fig. 12D). The rectum opens in the dorsoanterior wall.

Nervous system: Unpaired cerebral ganglion (60 μm long, 85 μm high, 110 μm wide) of oval cross-section. Buccal ganglia (15 μm long, 25 μm wide) in dorsal position to the radular region.

Table IV. Comparison of the species of the genus *Labidoherpia* Salvini-Plawen, 1978. Abbreviations: + present; - absent; ? unknown.

Tabla IV. Comparación de las especies del género Labidoherpia Salvini-Plawen, 1978. Abreviaturas: + presente; - ausente; ? desconocido.

	<i>L. spinosa</i>	<i>L. vituoi</i> n. sp.	<i>L. lucus</i> n. sp.
Distribution	Antarctica	NW Iberian Peninsula	NW Iberian Peninsula
Depth (m)	385	438 - 459	616
Length (mm)	7	3.68 - 5.62	3
Cuticle (μm)	75 - 100	50 - 70	25 - 35
Epidermal papillae	-	-	-
Multicellular forms	+	-	-
Pedal folds	1	3	3
Atriobuccal fold	+	+	-
Anterodorsal midgut caecum	paired	not paired	-
Radular denticles	2 - 3	6 - 7	3
Radular sac	support cells	muscular	simple
Oesophagus with sphincter	-	+	+
Midgut constrictions	+	+	-
Pericardium pouches	-	-	+
Heart position	dorsal wall	dorsal wall	unhooked
Seminal receptacles	+	+	+
Spawning duct pouches	?	+	+
Genital sphincter	-	+	-
Capulatory stylets	5	bundles	12
Muscular pouch	-	+	-
Pallial cavity pouches	-	-	ventral
Respiratory folds	14 - 16	8 - 9	4 - 6
Dorsoterminal sense organ	+	+	?

Large suprarectal commissure (75 μm long, 20 μm wide) located dorsally to the pericardioducts (Fig. 12A, B, D).

Sense organs: Branched atrial papillae in the atrium attached to the lateral and dorsal walls of the atrial cavity. No dorso-terminal sense organ was found.

Digestive system: Atrium and mouth in a common cavity, with no muscular groove separating them. The mouth continues in a long and narrow pharynx (185 μm long, 50 - 196 μm high, 45 - 70 μm wide) covered by a thin layer of cuticle and surrounded by musculature. A small dorso-pharyngeal gland (50 μm long, 25 - 30 μm high, 40 - 50 μm wide) opens into the pre-radular region of the

pharynx (Fig. 12A, D). Distichous radula. The teeth (15 μm long, 4 μm wide) bear a slightly curved distal hook and three triangular - shaped middle denticles, small, sharp, and broad-based (1 - 1.5 μm high, 0.5 - 1 μm wide at the base) (Fig. 12B). Small radular sac (30 μm long, 30 μm high, 25 μm wide) (Fig. 12B,D). Ventrolateral foregut glands type A (following SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ and SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2007) or type *Pararrhopalia* (following HANDL and TODT, 2005) formed by a narrow duct (80 μm long, 15 - 25 μm wide) (Fig. 12B-D). They open laterally into the radular region and then run posteriorly until reaching the midgut.

The oesophagus (55 μm long, 65 - 45 μm high, 60 - 40 μm wide) forms a sphincter in its posterior region (Fig. 12C, D). The midgut lacks serial constrictions and does not extend in an anterodorsal caecum. The rectum opens in the dorsal wall of the pallial cavity (Fig. 12D).

Gonopericardial system: Gonads with oocytes and spermatozoa in their posterior region. The specimen has a large blood sinus in the atrial region, with oval and nucleated blood cells. The pericardium (175 μm long, 30 μm high, 50 μm wide) extends in a 45 μm terminal pouch, dorsally to the rectum (Fig. 12D-F). The posterior region of the heart remains attached to the dorsal wall of the pericardium. A pair of small and high seminal receptacles (30 μm long, 25 μm high, 20 μm wide) can be observed at the connection of the pericardioducts with the spawning ducts (Fig. 12D, E). In the ventroposterior region of the spawning ducts, a pair of lateral pouches are observed which give them a trilobed aspect (Fig. 12D, F). The genital orifice opens into the dorsoanterior wall of the ventral pouch of the pallial cavity. With two bundles of 12 - 15 stylets copulatory stylets (245 μm long, 15 - 25 μm wide) (Fig. 12D-F). They run from the gonopericardioducts to the opening of the pallial cavity. The

entire length of the stylets is surrounded by musculature, but no muscle pouch is formed in their posterior region.

Taxonomical discussion: *Labidoherpia spinosa* (Thiele, 1913), described from Davis Sea in the Antarctica (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978) was the only described species of the genus. *Labidoherpia vitucoi* n. sp. and *Labidoherpia lucus* n. sp. (Table IV) differ from *Labidoherpia spinosa* (Thiele, 1913) (in addition to their wide geographical disparity) in having: a smaller body size, thinner cuticle, different composition of sclerites, three pedal folds, a sphincter in the oesophagus, anterodorsal caecum of the midgut not paired or absent, and fewer respiratory folds (THIELE, 1913; SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978). *Labidoherpia vitucoi* sp. nov and *Labidoherpia lucus* n. sp. come from the same geographical area and similar depth. There are several anatomical differences between them (Table IV), thus: *Labidoherpia vitucoi* n. sp. differs from *Labidoherpia lucus* n. sp. in having: a thicker cuticle and serrated sclerites, a muscular fold separating the atrium and mouth, teeth with more middle denticles, midgut with an anterodorsal caecum and constrictions, pallial cavity without pouches but more respiratory folds and muscular pouch of copulatory stylets.

TAXONOMICAL DISCUSSION ON THE FAMILY PRUVOTINIDAE

Pruvotiniidae is a complex family currently made up of five subfamilies and one subfamily incerta, characterized by the combination of the type of mantle sclerites, the presence or absence of a dorso-pharyngeal gland and the type of ventrolateral foregut glands (GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ AND SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2007).

The genus *Forcepimonia* Salvini-Plawen, 1969 is monospecific. *Forcepimonia protecta* Salvini-Plawen, 1969, was described from a specimen of the Red Sea from a depth of 30 m (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1969). Subsequently, this genus was classified within the subfamily

Lophomeniinae Salvini-Plawen, 1978 of the family Pruvotiniidae which is characterized by: lacking hook-shaped sclerites, bearing ventrolateral foregut glands of the pharynx type A and a dorso-pharyngeal gland (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ AND SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2007). The subfamily Halomeniinae Salvini-Plawen, 1978, like Lophomeniinae, has no hook-shaped sclerites and the ventrolateral foregut glands are type A. However, it differs from Lophomeniinae because it lacks a dorso-pharyngeal gland. The genus *Forcepimonia* is characterized by having a thin cuticle without epidermal papillae,

no hook-shaped sclerites, a distichous radula, ventrolateral foregut glands type A, constrictions in the midgut and copulatory stylets. In addition, no respiratory folds are known, and it lacks a dorsoterminal sense organ. However, since it lacks a dorso-pharyngeal gland (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2003), the genus *Forcepimentia* must be classified within the subfamily Halomeniinae.

The genus *Scheltemaia* Salvini-Plawen, 2003 is the only genus included in the subfamily incerta. Of this genus two species are described, *Scheltemaia bassensis* (Scheltema and Schander, 2000) and *Scheltemaia mimus* (Scheltema and Schander, 2000), both from Tasmania (Indian Ocean) and collected at depths of 70 and 140 m respectively (SCHELTEMA AND SCHANDER, 2000; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ AND SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2007). In the description of these two species SCHELTEMA AND SCHANDER (2000) classified them within the genus *Eleutheromenia* Salvini-Plawen, 1967 due to their distichous radula, copulatory stylets, and the absence of dorso-pharyngeal gland. Subsequently, when redescribing both species, SALVINI-PLAWEN (2003) concluded that they did not belong to the genus *Eleutheromenia* since they have

ventrolateral foregut glands of type C (type A in *Eleutheromenia*) and copulatory stylets (absent in *Eleutheromenia*). Since these characteristics did not allow him to classify these two species in any of the genera already described of the family Pruvotinidae, he created for them the genus *Scheltemaia* Salvini-Plawen, 2003 which he did not classify in any existing subfamily (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2003). By following the diagnostic criteria of the subfamilies of Pruvotinidae, based on the combination: presence/absence of hollow hook-shaped stylets, type of ventral glandular organs of the pharynx and presence/absence of the dorso-pharyngeal gland (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1978; GARCÍA-ÁLVAREZ AND SALVINI-PLAWEN, 2007), the creation of the new subfamily Scheltemaiinae is proposed here, in which the genus *Scheltemaia* is classified. The diagnosis of this subfamily as follows: with hollow hook-shaped acicular sclerites; with ventrolateral foregut glands of the pharynx type C; without dorso-pharyngeal gland.

In summary, with the proposed reclassification, the classification of the subfamilies and genus of the Pruvotinidae family results as follows:

Pruvotininae Heath, 1911 (= Pararrhopaliinae Salvini-Plawen, 1978)

Included genera: *Pararrhopalia* Simroth, 1893; *Pruvotina* Cockerell, 1903; *Labidoherpia* Salvini-Plawen, 1978.

Eleutheromeniinae Salvini-Plawen, 1978

Included genera: *Eleutheromenia* Salvini-Plawen, 1967; *Gephyroherpia* Salvini-Plawen, 1978; *Luitfriedia* García-Álvarez and Ugorri, 2001.

Lophomeniinae Salvini-Plawen, 1978

Included genera: *Lophomenia* Heath, 1911; *Metamenia* Thiele, 1913; *Hypomenia* Van Lummel, 1930.

Halomeniinae Salvini-Plawen, 1978

Included genera: *Halomenia* Heath, 1911; *Forcepimentia* Salvini-Plawen, 1969.

Unciherpiinae García-Álvarez, Salvini-Plawen and Ugorri, 2001

Included genera: *Uncimenia* Nierstrasz, 1903; *Sialoherpia* Salvini-Plawen, 1978; *Unciherpia* García-Álvarez, Salvini-Plawen and Ugorri, 2001.

Scheltemaiinae n. subfam.

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:AAA07FAA-3075-4DCC-9E13-7B0B84865073

Included genus: *Scheltemaia* Salvini-Plawen, 2003.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the scholarship 'Predoctoral Plan I 2C' of the 'Xunta de Galicia' (regional government) and 'C.E.I. Campus do Mar'. This paper is part of the following research projects carried out by the Estación de Biología Mariña da Graña (USC): PGIDT01PXI20008PR,

PGIDIT05 - PXIC20001P, PGIDIT07PXB000120PR, A SELVA - 08 and ForSaGal - 09 supported by the Dirección Xeral de I+D+i, Xunta de Galicia; VEM2003 - 20070 - C04 - 04, CGL 2004 - 22429 - E and CTM2004 - 00740 supported by the M.E.C, Government of Spain.

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